


```
##           49           50           51           52           53           54
## 4.284416e-04 1.071443e-02 9.798711e-06 1.284342e-01 1.916548e-10 2.391778e-06
##           55           56           57           58           59           60
## 2.807987e-06 6.804344e-09 5.605688e-02 1.568411e-02 3.786881e-03 7.598016e-06
##           61           62           63           64           65           66
## 8.359947e-13 3.727047e-01 5.688412e-06 8.491268e-08 2.201532e-04 4.578996e-06
##           67           68           69           70           71           72
## 7.502945e-04 2.119981e-05 6.332582e-02 1.349148e-07 3.208735e-08 1.353178e-08
##           73           74           75           76           77           78
## 1.470995e-03 5.333929e-10 3.184395e-05 7.525895e-02 9.999862e-01 9.999930e-01
##           79           80           81           82           83           84
## 9.020243e-02 9.969323e-01          NA 2.834561e-01 8.178839e-01 7.261971e-01
```

```
rocObj.ext.06.bio <- roc(visit6.ctrc[["Donor"]] ~ predict(ext.06.bio, type = "response"))
rocObj.ext.06.bio
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = visit6.ctrc[["Donor"]] ~ predict(ext.06.bio, type = "response"))
##
## Data: predict(ext.06.bio, type = "response") in 75 controls (visit6.ctrc[["Donor"]] TB Cures) < 7 ca
## Area under the curve: 0.9848
```

```
ci(rocObj.ext.06.bio, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.9591-1 (DeLong)
```

External validation of 6-month (basic characteristics and markers) signature

```
ext.06.comb <- glm(Donor ~ #Fever + PrevdiagTB + Tobaccolast6months + Severethinness +
  BCL2 + CD19 + CD3E + FCGR1A + IFITM3,# + IL1B + IL7R + NLRP1# + TLR5 + TLR6,
  data = visit6.ctrc, family = binomial, na.action = na.exclude)
summary(ext.06.comb)
```

```
##
## Call:
## glm(formula = Donor ~ BCL2 + CD19 + CD3E + FCGR1A + IFITM3, family = binomial,
## data = visit6.ctrc, na.action = na.exclude)
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -0.95377 -0.08708 -0.00419 -0.00041  2.26401
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## (Intercept) -3.678e-01  8.041e+00  -0.046   0.964
## BCL2         -2.858e-03  2.363e-03  -1.209   0.227
## CD19         -2.790e-03  2.175e-03  -1.282   0.200
## CD3E          1.203e-04  1.360e-04   0.885   0.376
## FCGR1A        1.656e-03  1.123e-03   1.475   0.140
## IFITM3        6.576e-06  1.342e-05   0.490   0.624
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
```

```

## Null deviance: 47.8360 on 81 degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance: 9.3805 on 76 degrees of freedom
## (2 observations deleted due to missingness)
## AIC: 21.381
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 10
# has redundant variables (with huge standard errors); therefore several variables were left out
rocObj.ext.06.comb <- roc(visit6.ctr[[ "Donor" ]] ~ predict(ext.06.comb, type = "response"))
rocObj.ext.06.comb

##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = visit6.ctr[[ "Donor" ]] ~ predict(ext.06.comb, type = "response"))
##
## Data: predict(ext.06.comb, type = "response") in 75 controls (visit6.ctr[[ "Donor" ]] TB Cures) < 7 c
## Area under the curve: 0.9905
ci(rocObj.ext.06.comb, of = "auc")

## 95% CI: 0.9701-1 (DeLong)

```

Early responders

Importing the data:

```

baseline.early.data <- read.csv("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treat
head(baseline.early.data)

```

```

##      PID Sample.ID      Donor      Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks Fever
## 1  20400 IPAX1413 Early Responders Training 54      1          1      1
## 2  260100 IPAX0303 Early Responders Training 50      1          1      1
## 3  360100 IPAX0313 Early Responders Training 70      2          1      1
## 4  950100 IPAX0749 Early Responders Training 70      1          1      1
## 5 1050100 IPAX0399 Early Responders Training 29      1          1      2
## 6 1380100 IPAX0087 Early Responders Training 35      1          1      1
##      Prevdia TB Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months BMI Severethinness CD14
## 1          2          2          2 16.99          2 17716
## 2          2          2          2 17.99          2 21725
## 3          2          2          2 13.14          1 19925
## 4          2          2          2 17.61          2  9090
## 5          2          1          1 15.98          1 20351
## 6          2          2          2 16.48          2 19093
##      CD4 IL4d2 BLR1 SEC14L1 TIMP2 MARCO CCL19 FPR1 IL4 NCAM1 FOXP3 CTLA4 RAB33A
## 1 2526  200  229  12305 25424  200  200 30485 200  143  200  641  200
## 2 2797  200 1105  22895 25938  200  200 28584 200  267  200  788  200
## 3 2542  200  444  16451 27271  200  200 39304 200  201  200  574  200
## 4 2480  200  534   9692 18008  200  200 16216 200  762  200 1077  200
## 5 4125  200 1165  11036 25159  200  200 32581 200  200  200  870  186
## 6 2421  200  342  12214 20249  200  200 29623 200  200  200  729  200
##      ABR TGFBR2 BCL2 CASP8 IL10 IL2RA SPP1 MMP9 RAB24 LTF CD163 TNFRSF1B CCL13
## 1 3964  2454  253  5134  272  200  200 2578 6222 869  274  3887  200
## 2 4764  4661  740  4252  200  216  200 2210 3851 258  627  4790  200

```



```

## 1 13919 3287 2244 2305 3911 22141 200 1101 200 12249 1468 12138 3300
## 2 4802 6859 1183 1434 769 3370 200 670 200 6097 1129 7718 2073
## 3 32034 4831 7841 3076 9422 14216 1645 6080 200 11686 2638 16316 4145
## 4 14025 13797 2408 2685 1147 4599 200 1212 200 7294 1063 8545 2938
## 5 30737 9779 5120 2875 6763 19232 1132 4712 200 10423 2193 13653 4286
## 6 8002 5164 1589 1971 1652 9905 200 676 200 5772 1807 11654 3442
## B2M GBP1 CCL3 ASAP1 HCK BMP6 CXCL9 KIF1B HPRT DSE EGF CCL11 CX3CL1
## 1 89534 3298 1847 5394 19569 5325 200 4272 200 892 288 13510 209
## 2 22566 940 1448 7433 26997 6474 200 3253 200 1207 200 10682 200
## 3 33353 3279 989 6726 23612 4474 200 3778 200 1166 200 7040 144
## 4 54116 1241 3552 6914 17794 10130 200 4762 200 200 200 175448 1214
## 5 53843 2096 1504 7538 25237 6722 200 3512 200 1267 200 16125 200
## 6 56962 1289 1046 6880 18051 6307 200 3343 200 1008 200 10685 200
## IL6 INDO LYN SLAMF7 TNIP1 VEGF
## 1 2676 200 16362 2054 2626 291
## 2 2774 276 18984 1614 3874 361
## 3 2353 200 21477 1256 2756 293
## 4 4324 200 15696 3991 2098 200
## 5 2459 200 18797 1587 3604 446
## 6 2753 200 14401 1382 2685 272

```

```
dim(baseline.early.data)
```

```
## [1] 90 160
```

```
visit2.early.data <- read.csv("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment")
```

```
dim(visit2.early.data)
```

```
## [1] 67 160
```

Combining baseline and visit 2 data:

```
names(baseline.early.data) == names(visit2.early.data)
```

```

## [1] TRUE TRUE
## [16] TRUE TRUE
## [31] TRUE TRUE
## [46] TRUE TRUE
## [61] TRUE TRUE
## [76] TRUE TRUE
## [91] TRUE TRUE
## [106] TRUE TRUE
## [121] TRUE TRUE
## [136] TRUE TRUE
## [151] TRUE TRUE

```

```

combined.early.data <- rbind(baseline.early.data, visit2.early.data)
combined.early.data[["Visit"]] <- c(rep(0, nrow(baseline.early.data)),
                                     rep(2, nrow(visit2.early.data)))

```

```

levels(combined.early.data[["Donor"]]) <- c("Cure", "Fail")
combined.early.data[["dovi"]] <- with(combined.early.data, interaction(Donor, Visit))

```

```

combined.early.data[["Gender"]] <- combined.early.data[["Gender"]] - 1
combined.early.data[["Cough.2weeks"]] <- combined.early.data[["Cough.2weeks"]] - 1
combined.early.data[["Fever"]] <- combined.early.data[["Fever"]] - 1

```


Doing a loop where linear mixed models are fitted. The linear mixed models don't include any covariate adjustments as we want to identify as many biomarkers as possible.

```
contrastMat2 <- matrix(0, 1, 2)
contrastMat2[1, c(1, 2)] <- c(-1, 1)

resultsMat.early <- matrix(NA, 147, 6)
for (i in 14:160)
{
  #print(names(combined.data)[i])
  #print(yVec)
  yVec <- combined.early.data[, i]
  if (mean(yVec > 200) > 0.1)
  {
    lmmModel <- survreg(Surv(log2(yVec), yVec > 200, type = "left") ~ dovi-1 + frailty.gaussian(PID),
                      dist = "gaussian", data = combined.early.data)
    #print(lmmModel)
    lmmComp1 <- try(summary(glht(parm(coef(lmmModel)[1:2], vcov(lmmModel)[1:2, 1:2]),
                                linfct = contrastMat[1, 1:2, drop = FALSE]))[["test"]])
    lmmComp2 <- try(summary(glht(parm(coef(lmmModel)[3:4], vcov(lmmModel)[3:4, 3:4]),
                                linfct = contrastMat[1, 1:2, drop = FALSE]))[["test"]])

    if (!inherits(lmmComp1, "try-error")) {
      resultsMat.early[i-13, 1:3] <- c(lmmComp1[["coefficients"]], lmmComp1[["sigma"]],
                                      lmmComp1[["pvalues"]])
    }
    if (!inherits(lmmComp2, "try-error")) {
      resultsMat.early[i-13, 4:6] <- c(lmmComp2[["coefficients"]], lmmComp2[["sigma"]],
                                      lmmComp2[["pvalues"]])
    }
  }
}
colnames(resultsMat.early) <- c("Est.0", "SE.0", "p.0", "Est.02", "SE.02", "p.02")
rownames(resultsMat.early) <- names(combined.early.data)[14:160]
head(resultsMat.early)
```

```
##           Est.0      SE.0      p.0      Est.02      SE.02      p.02
## CD14      -5.2595909 0.06424902 0.0000000 -0.01258012 0.07507024 0.86691524
## CD4       0.1472344 0.13086645 0.2605579 -0.20810721 0.15174710 0.17024776
## IL4d2           NA           NA           NA           NA           NA           NA
## BLR1      -0.3087743 0.20293911 0.1281314 -0.41185404 0.21082723 0.05075866
## SEC14L1   -0.1559927 0.12107967 0.1976250 -0.04679040 0.14146725 0.74083275
## TIMP2     -32.7996783 0.06903944 0.0000000 0.06208530 0.10249298 0.54467966
```

```
dim(resultsMat.early)
```

```
## [1] 147 6
```

```
## Removing 2 markers with 0 SE
```

```
resultsMat.early <- resultsMat.early[!(row.names(resultsMat.early) %in% c("CD8A", "TIMP2")), ]
dim(resultsMat.early)
```

```
## [1] 145 6
```

```
pval.00.early <- resultsMat.early[, "p.0"]
resultsMat.00.early <- resultsMat.early[!is.na(pval.00.early), 1:3]
head(resultsMat.00.early, 20)
```

```
##           Est.0      SE.0      p.0
## CD14      -5.259590911 0.06424902 0.0000000000
## CD4       0.147234365 0.13086645 0.2605579281
## BLR1     -0.308774266 0.20293911 0.1281314413
## SEC14L1  -0.155992704 0.12107967 0.1976249849
## FPR1     -4.880052959 0.06136460 0.0000000000
## NCAM1    -0.637206163 0.27073923 0.0185936570
## FOXP3     0.400318859 0.55658115 0.4719892543
## CTLA4    -0.147933335 0.04430726 0.0008413938
## RAB33A   -0.131575719 0.14755223 0.3725414059
## ABR      -4.809726851 0.05515118 0.0000000000
## TGFBR2   -2.563822499 0.06169864 0.0000000000
## BCL2     -0.282818370 0.12864107 0.0279129583
## CASP8    -3.172719720 0.05328868 0.0000000000
## IL10      0.220049638 0.16047718 0.1703061433
## IL2RA    -0.888364342 0.66238756 0.1798701564
## MMP9     -0.252352478 0.20701422 0.2228402519
## RAB24    -4.427232852 0.05519102 0.0000000000
## LTF      -0.126839493 0.25578331 0.6199744887
## CD163    -0.006367772 0.14121746 0.9640340116
## TNFRSF1B -3.938685621 0.05270157 0.0000000000
```

```
nrow(resultsMat.00.early)
```

```
## [1] 112
```

```
resultsMat.early.0a <- resultsMat.00.early[resultsMat.00.early[, "p.0"] < 0.05, ]
head(resultsMat.early.0a)
```

```
##           Est.0      SE.0      p.0
## CD14      -5.2595909 0.06424902 0.0000000000
## FPR1     -4.8800530 0.06136460 0.0000000000
## NCAM1    -0.6372062 0.27073923 0.0185936570
## CTLA4    -0.1479333 0.04430726 0.0008413938
## ABR      -4.8097269 0.05515118 0.0000000000
## TGFBR2   -2.5638225 0.06169864 0.0000000000
```

```
dim(resultsMat.early.0a)
```

```
## [1] 60  3
```

```
pval.02.early <- resultsMat.early[, "p.02"]
resultsMat.02.early <- resultsMat.early[!is.na(pval.02.early), 4:6]
head(resultsMat.02.early, 20)
```

```
##           Est.02      SE.02      p.02
## CD14      -0.012580125 0.07507024 0.86691524
## CD4       -0.208107207 0.15174710 0.17024776
## BLR1     -0.411854041 0.21082723 0.05075866
## SEC14L1  -0.046790402 0.14146725 0.74083275
## FPR1     -0.001881097 0.07169955 0.97906924
## NCAM1    -0.631736344 0.28488688 0.02658902
## FOXP3    -0.250533514 0.60459523 0.67859421
## CTLA4    -0.113978519 0.05114293 0.02583874
## RAB33A    0.188223777 0.16156626 0.24402128
## ABR       0.006453261 0.06443839 0.92022824
## TGFBR2    0.047522897 0.07156201 0.50663911
```

```
## BCL2      -0.356864108 0.14413382 0.01328926
## CASP8     0.016413976 0.06226172 0.79206603
## IL10      0.057060529 0.17074202 0.73823507
## IL2RA     1.163757955 1.06734420 0.27556758
## MMP9      0.332820905 0.23339831 0.15387462
## RAB24     0.010568655 0.06448494 0.86981509
## LTF       -0.099182881 0.30259137 0.74307931
## CD163     -0.026262200 0.15991212 0.86955091
## TNFRSF1B  0.005387331 0.06157557 0.93028094
```

```
nrow(resultsMat.02.early)
```

```
## [1] 112
```

```
resultsMat.early.2a <- resultsMat.02.early[resultsMat.02.early[, "p.02"] < 0.05, ]
head(resultsMat.early.2a)
```

```
##           Est.02      SE.02      p.02
## NCAM1 -0.6317363 0.28488688 0.026589016
## CTLA4 -0.1139785 0.05114293 0.025838736
## BCL2  -0.3568641 0.14413382 0.013289260
## RAB13 -0.5162345 0.22607840 0.022404971
## GZMA  -0.7263252 0.22451683 0.001216175
## GNLY  -0.5163073 0.16814645 0.002136425
```

```
dim(resultsMat.early.2a)
```

```
## [1] 19  3
```

```
print(xtable(resultsMat.early[order(rownames(resultsMat.early)), ], digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/first")
```

Identifying significant differences:

```
pval.00.early <- resultsMat.early[, "p.0"]
resultsMat.00.early <- resultsMat.early[!is.na(pval.00.early), 1:3]
head(resultsMat.00.early, 20)
```

```
##           Est.0      SE.0      p.0
## CD14      -5.259590911 0.06424902 0.0000000000
## CD4        0.147234365 0.13086645 0.2605579281
## BLR1      -0.308774266 0.20293911 0.1281314413
## SEC14L1   -0.155992704 0.12107967 0.1976249849
## FPR1      -4.880052959 0.06136460 0.0000000000
## NCAM1     -0.637206163 0.27073923 0.0185936570
## FOXP3     0.400318859 0.55658115 0.4719892543
## CTLA4     -0.147933335 0.04430726 0.0008413938
## RAB33A    -0.131575719 0.14755223 0.3725414059
## ABR       -4.809726851 0.05515118 0.0000000000
## TGFBR2    -2.563822499 0.06169864 0.0000000000
## BCL2      -0.282818370 0.12864107 0.0279129583
## CASP8     -3.172719720 0.05328868 0.0000000000
## IL10      0.220049638 0.16047718 0.1703061433
## IL2RA     -0.888364342 0.66238756 0.1798701564
## MMP9      -0.252352478 0.20701422 0.2228402519
## RAB24     -4.427232852 0.05519102 0.0000000000
## LTF       -0.126839493 0.25578331 0.6199744887
## CD163     -0.006367772 0.14121746 0.9640340116
```

```
## TNFRSF1B -3.938685621 0.05270157 0.0000000000
```

```
nrow(resultsMat.00.early)
```

```
## [1] 112
```

```
resultsMat.early.0a <- resultsMat.00.early[resultsMat.00.early[, "p.0"] < 0.05, ]  
head(resultsMat.early.0a)
```

```
##           Est.0       SE.0         p.0  
## CD14      -5.2595909 0.06424902 0.0000000000  
## FPR1      -4.8800530 0.06136460 0.0000000000  
## NCAM1     -0.6372062 0.27073923 0.0185936570  
## CTLA4     -0.1479333 0.04430726 0.0008413938  
## ABR       -4.8097269 0.05515118 0.0000000000  
## TGFBR2    -2.5638225 0.06169864 0.0000000000
```

```
dim(resultsMat.early.0a)
```

```
## [1] 60 3
```

```
pval.02.early <- resultsMat.early[, "p.02"]  
resultsMat.02.early <- resultsMat.early[!is.na(pval.02.early), 4:6]  
head(resultsMat.02.early, 20)
```

```
##           Est.02      SE.02         p.02  
## CD14      -0.012580125 0.07507024 0.86691524  
## CD4       -0.208107207 0.15174710 0.17024776  
## BLR1      -0.411854041 0.21082723 0.05075866  
## SEC14L1   -0.046790402 0.14146725 0.74083275  
## FPR1      -0.001881097 0.07169955 0.97906924  
## NCAM1     -0.631736344 0.28488688 0.02658902  
## FOXP3     -0.250533514 0.60459523 0.67859421  
## CTLA4     -0.113978519 0.05114293 0.02583874  
## RAB33A    0.188223777 0.16156626 0.24402128  
## ABR       0.006453261 0.06443839 0.92022824  
## TGFBR2    0.047522897 0.07156201 0.50663911  
## BCL2     -0.356864108 0.14413382 0.01328926  
## CASP8     0.016413976 0.06226172 0.79206603  
## IL10      0.057060529 0.17074202 0.73823507  
## IL2RA     1.163757955 1.06734420 0.27556758  
## MMP9      0.332820905 0.23339831 0.15387462  
## RAB24     0.010568655 0.06448494 0.86981509  
## LTF       -0.099182881 0.30259137 0.74307931  
## CD163     -0.026262200 0.15991212 0.86955091  
## TNFRSF1B  0.005387331 0.06157557 0.93028094
```

```
nrow(resultsMat.02.early)
```

```
## [1] 112
```

```
resultsMat.early.2a <- resultsMat.02.early[resultsMat.02.early[, "p.02"] < 0.05, ]  
head(resultsMat.early.2a)
```

```
##           Est.02      SE.02         p.02  
## NCAM1    -0.6317363 0.28488688 0.026589016  
## CTLA4    -0.1139785 0.05114293 0.025838736  
## BCL2    -0.3568641 0.14413382 0.013289260
```

```
## RAB13 -0.5162345 0.22607840 0.022404971
## GZMA -0.7263252 0.22451683 0.001216175
## GNLY -0.5163073 0.16814645 0.002136425
```

```
dim(resultsMat.early.2a)
```

```
## [1] 19 3
```

Early responders - prediction at baseline

Defining and showing baseline data:

```
train.00.early.1 <-
  cbind(baseline.early.data[, 1:13], baseline.early.data[, rownames(resultsMat.early.0a)])
```

```
head(train.00.early.1)
```

```
##      PID Sample.ID      Donor      Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks Fever
## 1  20400 IPAX1413 Early Responders Training 54      1      1      1
## 2  260100 IPAX0303 Early Responders Training 50      1      1      1
## 3  360100 IPAX0313 Early Responders Training 70      2      1      1
## 4  950100 IPAX0749 Early Responders Training 70      1      1      1
## 5 1050100 IPAX0399 Early Responders Training 29      1      1      2
## 6 1380100 IPAX0087 Early Responders Training 35      1      1      1
##      PrevdiagTB Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months      BMI Severethinness      CD14
## 1      2      2      2      2 16.99      2 17716
## 2      2      2      2      2 17.99      2 21725
## 3      2      2      2      2 13.14      1 19925
## 4      2      2      2      2 17.61      2 9090
## 5      2      1      1      1 15.98      1 20351
## 6      2      2      2      2 16.48      2 19093
##      FPR1 NCAM1 CTLA4  ABR  TGFBR2  BCL2  CASP8  RAB24  TNFRSF1B  TNFRSF1A  RAB13  CD19
## 1 30485  143   641 3964   2454  253  5134  6222   3887   14431  200  213
## 2 28584  267   788 4764   4661  740  4252  3851   4790   17669  195  302
## 3 39304  201   574 4804   5925  352  6187  7173   6601   22511  129  299
## 4 16216  762  1077 3574   3699  517  6490  3413   3461   15938  613  200
## 5 32581  200   870 4243   3778  949  4865  4185   6274   22122  295  490
## 6 29623  200   729 3898   3263  332  3455  4316   3959   18439  150  317
##      TNF  TGFB1  GNLY  GZMB  PRF1  PTPRCv1  PTPRCv2  CCL4  CD3E  CD209  NLRP1  CXCL13  TLR6
## 1 1160 28197 15631 1974 1982      867  13963  294 1239  3245  3236  1286 2378
## 2  827 43272 15761 1498 4726      3114  7667  590 2935  2812  4521  1649 3022
## 3 1045 39602 15293 2421 4801      1362 13434  645 1519  2149  6723  1730 5281
## 4 1100 45837 58366 8805 14623  6229  9173 1028 5207  5460  7604  1686 2757
## 5 1295 52602 10429 1744 3678      3613  9705  572 3442  3788  7334  1640 3449
## 6  818 36435 25968 3132 3594      2243 10857  331 1462  3476  6702  1541 1499
##      NOD1  CCL5  TLR7  TAGAP  NLRC4  TLR8  NOD2  TLR4  CLEC7A  TLR1  FLCN1  IFI35  GBP2
## 1  558 16678  817 8270  1941 6047  593 2930 10587 5369  200 10257 43736
## 2  943 16291 1152 7807  1594  865 1047 1876  7092 4711  200 10382 23400
## 3  804 14524  943 11510 1526 4864 1635 2451  7378 4898  216 10222 46588
## 4 1789 40896  955 12791 1326  937  666 2393 12867 5511  292 11715 24069
## 5 1011 14181 1228  7813 1257  788  989 3812 11148 6145  200 10905 41880
## 6  998 25545 1078  8572 1212  945  769 4363  8709 2917  232 11842 30250
##      IFIT3  CXCL10  IFI16  IFIT2  IL7R  OAS1  IFIH1  STAT1  STAT2  TAP1  TAP2  B2M  ASAP1
## 1  8101  657  37304 13501 3287 2244  2305 12249  1468 12138 3300 89534  5394
## 2  3597  728  32227  7350 6859 1183  1434  6097  1129  7718 2073 22566  7433
```

```
## 3 14688    200  32540 20924  4831 7841  3076 11686  2638 16316 4145 33353  6726
## 4  7052   1587 216836 10355 13797 2408  2685  7294  1063  8545 2938 54116  6914
## 5 12545    200  42891 19503  9779 5120  2875 10423  2193 13653 4286 53843  7538
## 6  4092    200  29778  6595  5164 1589  1971  5772  1807 11654 3442 56962  6880
##      HCK  BMP6 KIF1B  DSE INDO    LYN SLAMF7 TNIP1
## 1 19569  5325  4272  892  200 16362  2054  2626
## 2 26997  6474  3253 1207  276 18984  1614  3874
## 3 23612  4474  3778 1166  200 21477  1256  2756
## 4 17794 10130  4762  200  200 15696  3991  2098
## 5 25237  6722  3512 1267  200 18797  1587  3604
## 6 18051  6307  3343 1008  200 14401  1382  2685
```

```
dim(train.00.early.1)
```

```
## [1] 90 73
```

P

Fitting a LASSO logistic regression model only using basic participant characteristics (no marker data, only information about age, gender, cough (past 2 weeks), fever, previous diagnosed TB, tobacco (last 6 months), alcohol (past 6 months), BMI, and severe thinness):

```
set.seed(201907021)
lassoTrainResults00.early.0a <- lassoTrain(train.00.early.1[, c(5:13)],
                                          train.00.early.1[, 3], skipVar = 1:10)
lassoTrainResults00.early.0a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 10 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##                1  1
## (Intercept)    4.96724526 NA
## Age            -0.01863679 NA
## Gender         -0.34686568 NA
## Cough.2weeks   0.00000000 NA
## Fever          0.00000000 NA
## PrevdiaqTB    -0.88383745 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.36204238 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.63923515 NA
## BMI           0.00000000 NA
## Severethinness 0.00000000 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.early.0a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 6 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##                1  1
## (Intercept)    4.96724526 NA
## Age            -0.01863679 NA
## Gender         -0.34686568 NA
## PrevdiaqTB    -0.88383745 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.36204238 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.63923515 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.early.0b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults00.early.0a,
                                                train.00.early.1[, c(5:13)], train.00.early.1[, 3],
                                                "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
```

```
rocObj.00.early.0 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.early.0b[["pred"]])
```

```
rocObj.00.early.0
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.early.0b[["pred"]])  
##  
## Data: X1 in 32 controls (truth Early Responders) < 58 cases (truth Non Responders).  
## Area under the curve: 0.7656
```

```
ci(rocObj.00.early.0, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.6625-0.8688 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.early <- matrix(NA, 3, 9)  
aucMat.early[1, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.00.early.0, of = "auc")
```

P+B

Fitting LASSO to basic participant characteristics and the selection of identified biomarkers (from step 1) using the criterion p-value less than 0.05:

```
set.seed(201907022)
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.early.1a <- lassoTrain(train.00.early.1[, -c(1:4)],  
                                         train.00.early.1[, 3], skipVar = 1:10)  
lassoTrainResults00.early.1a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 70 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
```

```
##              1  1  
## (Intercept)  8.325792e+00 NA  
## Age         -2.768834e-02 NA  
## Gender      -4.980854e-01 NA  
## Cough.2weeks .          NA  
## Fever       .          NA  
## PrevdiagTB -1.915160e+00 NA  
## Tobaccolast6months -1.150044e-01 NA  
## Alcoholpast6months -1.033800e+00 NA  
## BMI         .          NA  
## Severethinness .          NA  
## CD14        1.129890e-04  1  
## FPR1        .          .  
## NCAM1       .          .  
## CTLA4       6.366240e-04  8  
## ABR         -1.998357e-04  3  
## TGFBR2     .          .  
## BCL2       .          .  
## CASP8      3.227960e-05  0  
## RAB24      .          .  
## TNFRSF1B   .          .  
## TNFRSF1A   .          .  
## RAB13     -5.528098e-04  7  
## CD19      .          .  
## TNF       .          .  
## TGFB1    -3.405436e-05  0  
## GNLY     -1.982063e-05  0
```

```

## GZMB . .
## PRF1 . .
## PTPRCv1 . .
## PTPRCv2 . .
## CCL4 . .
## CD3E . .
## CD209 . .
## NLRP1 . .
## CXCL13 . .
## TLR6 . .
## NOD1 . .
## CCL5 . .
## TLR7 1.118689e-03 14
## TAGAP . .
## NLRC4 1.979446e-03 25
## TLR8 . .
## NOD2 . .
## TLR4 -5.711420e-04 7
## CLEC7A . .
## TLR1 . .
## FLCN1 . .
## IFI35 . .
## GBP2 -1.712228e-05 0
## IFIT3 . .
## CXCL10 -1.111306e-03 14
## IFI16 . .
## IFIT2 . .
## IL7R . .
## OAS1 . .
## IFIH1 . .
## STAT1 . .
## STAT2 . .
## TAP1 . .
## TAP2 . .
## B2M 1.093422e-05 0
## ASAP1 . .
## HCK . .
## BMP6 . .
## KIF1B . .
## DSE -8.576758e-04 11
## INDO . .
## LYN . .
## SLAMF7 . .
## TNIP1 -5.144031e-04 7

```

```
lassoTrainResults00.early.1a[["red.coef"]]
```

```

## 21 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##           1  1
## (Intercept)  8.325792e+00 NA
## Age -2.768834e-02 NA
## Gender -4.980854e-01 NA
## Prevdia TB -1.915160e+00 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -1.150044e-01 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -1.033800e+00 NA

```

```
## CD14          1.129890e-04  1
## CTLA4        6.366240e-04  8
## ABR          -1.998357e-04  3
## CASP8        3.227960e-05  0
## RAB13        -5.528098e-04  7
## TGFB1        -3.405436e-05  0
## GNLY         -1.982063e-05  0
## TLR7         1.118689e-03 14
## NLRC4        1.979446e-03 25
## TLR4         -5.711420e-04  7
## GBP2         -1.712228e-05  0
## CXCL10       -1.111306e-03 14
## B2M          1.093422e-05  0
## DSE          -8.576758e-04 11
## TNIP1        -5.144031e-04  7
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.early.1b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults00.early.1a,
                                              train.00.early.1[, -c(1:4)], train.00.early.1[, 3],
                                              "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
```

```
rocObj.00.early.1 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.early.1b[["pred"]])
rocObj.00.early.1
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.early.1b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 32 controls (truth Early Responders) < 58 cases (truth Non Responders).
## Area under the curve: 0.9709
```

```
ci(rocObj.00.early.1, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.9432-0.9986 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.early[2, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.00.early.1, of = "auc")
```

B

Fitting LASSO to selection of identified biomarkers without the basic participant characteristics:

```
set.seed(201907023)
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.early.2a <- lassoTrain(train.00.early.1[, -c(1:13)],
                                         train.00.early.1[, 3])
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.early.2a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 61 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
```

```
##          1  1
## (Intercept) 6.112037e-01 NA
## CD14          .      .
## FPR1          .      .
## NCAM1         .      .
## CTLA4         .      .
## ABR           .      .
## TGFBR2        .      .
## BCL2          .      .
```

```

## CASP8 . .
## RAB24 . .
## TNFRSF1B . .
## TNFRSF1A . .
## RAB13 . .
## CD19 . .
## TNF . .
## TGFB1 . .
## GNLY . .
## GZMB . .
## PRF1 . .
## PTPRCv1 . .
## PTPRCv2 . .
## CCL4 -2.757538e-05 100
## CD3E . .
## CD209 . .
## NLRP1 . .
## CXCL13 . .
## TLR6 . .
## NOD1 . .
## CCL5 . .
## TLR7 . .
## TAGAP . .
## NLRC4 . .
## TLR8 . .
## NOD2 . .
## TLR4 . .
## CLEC7A . .
## TLR1 . .
## FLCN1 . .
## IFI35 . .
## GBP2 . .
## IFIT3 . .
## CXCL10 . .
## IFI16 . .
## IFIT2 . .
## IL7R . .
## OAS1 . .
## IFIH1 . .
## STAT1 . .
## STAT2 . .
## TAP1 . .
## TAP2 . .
## B2M . .
## ASAP1 . .
## HCK . .
## BMP6 . .
## KIF1B . .
## DSE . .
## INDO . .
## LYN . .
## SLAMF7 . .
## TNIP1 . .

```

```

lassoTrainResults00.early.2a[["red.coef"]]

## 2 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##           1  1
## (Intercept) 6.112037e-01 NA
## CCL4      -2.757538e-05 100

lassoTrainResults00.early.2b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults00.early.2a,
                                              train.00.early.1[, -c(1:13)], train.00.early.1[, 3],
                                              "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")

rocObj.00.early.2 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.early.2b[["pred"]])
rocObj.00.early.2

##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.early.2b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 32 controls (truth Early Responders) < 58 cases (truth Non Responders).
## Area under the curve: 0.6705

ci(rocObj.00.early.2, of = "auc")

## 95% CI: 0.5462-0.7949 (DeLong)

aucMat.early[3, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.00.early.2, of = "auc")

list.00.early <- list(
  Basic = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.early.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  BasicMarker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.early.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Marker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.early.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE])

idx.00.early <- Reduce(union, lapply(list.00.early, rownames))

combinedMat.00.early <- do.call(cbind, lapply(list.00.early, "[", idx.00.early, ))
# code modified after:
# https://stackoverflow.com/questions/16808269/combine-data-frames-in-r-using-only-common-row-names
rownames(combinedMat.00.early) <- idx.00.early
combinedMat.00.early

##           Basic  BasicMarker  Marker
## (Intercept) 4.96724526 8.325792e+00 6.112037e-01
## Age        -0.01863679 -2.768834e-02      NA
## Gender     -0.34686568 -4.980854e-01      NA
## PrevdiagTB -0.88383745 -1.915160e+00      NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.36204238 -1.150044e-01      NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.63923515 -1.033800e+00      NA
## CD14        NA 1.129890e-04      NA
## CTLA4        NA 6.366240e-04      NA
## ABR          NA -1.998357e-04      NA
## CASP8        NA 3.227960e-05      NA
## RAB13        NA -5.528098e-04      NA
## TGFB1        NA -3.405436e-05      NA
## GNLY         NA -1.982063e-05      NA
## TLR7         NA 1.118689e-03      NA
## NLRC4        NA 1.979446e-03      NA

```

```
## TLR4          NA -5.711420e-04          NA
## GBP2          NA -1.712228e-05          NA
## CXCL10        NA -1.111306e-03          NA
## B2M           NA  1.093422e-05          NA
## DSE           NA -8.576758e-04          NA
## TNIP1         NA -5.144031e-04          NA
## CCL4          NA                NA -2.757538e-05
```

```
combinedMat.00.early[-c(1:6), ] <- 1000*combinedMat.00.early[-c(1:6), ]
```

```
combined.00.early.mark <- combinedMat.00.early[-c(1:6), ]
combined.00.early.mark <- combined.00.early.mark[order(row.names(combined.00.early.mark)), ]
combinedMat.00.early <- rbind(combinedMat.00.early[1:6, ], combined.00.early.mark)
combinedMat.00.early
```

##	Basic	BasicMarker	Marker
## (Intercept)	4.96724526	8.32579240	0.61120374
## Age	-0.01863679	-0.02768834	NA
## Gender	-0.34686568	-0.49808541	NA
## PrevdiagTB	-0.88383745	-1.91516004	NA
## Tobaccolast6months	-0.36204238	-0.11500436	NA
## Alcoholpast6months	-0.63923515	-1.03380015	NA
## ABR	NA	-0.19983575	NA
## B2M	NA	0.01093422	NA
## CASP8	NA	0.03227960	NA
## CCL4	NA	NA	-0.02757538
## CD14	NA	0.11298905	NA
## CTLA4	NA	0.63662399	NA
## CXCL10	NA	-1.11130646	NA
## DSE	NA	-0.85767578	NA
## GBP2	NA	-0.01712228	NA
## GNLY	NA	-0.01982063	NA
## NLRC4	NA	1.97944640	NA
## RAB13	NA	-0.55280976	NA
## TGFB1	NA	-0.03405436	NA
## TLR4	NA	-0.57114201	NA
## TLR7	NA	1.11868886	NA
## TNIP1	NA	-0.51440306	NA

```
print(xtable(combinedMat.00.early, digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/combinedMat.00.early.html")
```

```
list.02XX <- list(
  Patient00 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Biomarker00 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient.Biomarker00 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient02 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Biomarker02 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient.Biomarker02 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient00.E = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.early.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Biomarker00.E = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.early.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient.Biomarker00.E = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.early.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE])
```

```
pat.names <- c("(Intercept)", "Age", "Alcoholpast6months", "BMI", "Gender", "Cough.2weeks", "Fever", "Patient00", "Patient02", "Patient00.E", "Patient02.E", "Severethinness", "Tobaccolast6months")
```

```

pat.dat <- data.frame(pat.names)
row.names(pat.dat) <- pat.names

idx.02X <-
  Reduce(union, lapply(list(pat.dat,
    list.02XX[["Patient00"]], list.02XX[["Patient02"]],
    list.02XX[["Patient00.E"]], list.02XX[["Patient.Biomarker00"]],
    list.02XX[["Patient.Biomarker02"]], list.02XX[["Patient.Biomarker00.E"]],
    list.02XX[["Biomarker00"]], list.02XX[["Biomarker02"]],
    list.02XX[["Biomarker00.E"]]), rownames))
idx.02X

```

```

## [1] "(Intercept)"      "Age"                "Alcoholpast6months"
## [4] "BMI"                "Gender"              "Cough.2weeks"
## [7] "Fever"              "PrevdiagTB"         "Severethinness"
## [10] "Tobaccolast6months" "NCAM1"              "CD19"
## [13] "AIRE"               "NLRP1"              "CXCL13"
## [16] "TLR6"               "NLRP2"              "NLRC4"
## [19] "TLR8"               "NOD2"               "CXCL10"
## [22] "B2M"               "BCL2"               "IL13"
## [25] "STAT2"             "CD14"               "CTLA4"
## [28] "ABR"               "CASP8"              "RAB13"
## [31] "TGFB1"             "GNLY"               "TLR7"
## [34] "TLR4"               "GBP2"               "DSE"
## [37] "TNIP1"             "PTPRCv1"           "TAP2"
## [40] "CD3E"              "CCL4"

```

```
idx.02XX <- c(idx.02X[1:10], sort(idx.02X[-c(1:10)]))
```

```

idx.02XX
## [1] "(Intercept)"      "Age"                "Alcoholpast6months"
## [4] "BMI"                "Gender"              "Cough.2weeks"
## [7] "Fever"              "PrevdiagTB"         "Severethinness"
## [10] "Tobaccolast6months" "ABR"                "AIRE"
## [13] "B2M"               "BCL2"               "CASP8"
## [16] "CCL4"              "CD14"               "CD19"
## [19] "CD3E"              "CTLA4"              "CXCL10"
## [22] "CXCL13"           "DSE"                "GBP2"
## [25] "GNLY"              "IL13"               "NCAM1"
## [28] "NLRC4"             "NLRP1"              "NLRP2"
## [31] "NOD2"              "PTPRCv1"            "RAB13"
## [34] "STAT2"             "TAP2"               "TGFB1"
## [37] "TLR4"              "TLR6"               "TLR7"
## [40] "TLR8"              "TNIP1"

```

```

combinedMat.02XX <- do.call(cbind, lapply(list.02XX, "[", idx.02XX, ))
# code modified after:
# https://stackoverflow.com/questions/16808269/combine-data-frames-in-r-using-only-common-row-names
rownames(combinedMat.02XX) <- idx.02XX
combinedMat.02XX

```

```

##           Patient00   Biomarker00 Patient.Biomarker00   Patient02
## (Intercept)  1.119987416 1.360445e+00      2.624837e+00  3.18672402
## Age          -0.002848961          NA                  NA -0.00414461
## Alcoholpast6months -0.438961554          NA      -2.521741e-01 -0.32204999

```

## BMI	NA	NA	NA	-0.16414879
## Gender	-0.929178034	NA	-5.898818e-01	-0.39897567
## Cough.2weeks	NA	NA	NA	NA
## Fever	NA	NA	NA	NA
## PrevdiaqTB	-0.409437200	NA	-2.526728e-01	-0.29770279
## Severethinness	-0.841756922	NA	-5.384958e-01	-0.27184624
## Tobaccolast6months	-0.572536506	NA	-3.560233e-01	-0.55553903
## ABR	NA	NA	NA	NA
## AIRE	NA	-8.898295e-04	-1.537901e-03	NA
## B2M	NA	NA	2.660980e-07	NA
## BCL2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CASP8	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CCL4	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CD14	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CD19	NA	-3.667623e-04	-4.572906e-04	NA
## CD3E	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CTLA4	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CXCL10	NA	NA	-7.612117e-05	NA
## CXCL13	NA	-9.357238e-05	-1.847069e-04	NA
## DSE	NA	NA	NA	NA
## GBP2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## GNLY	NA	NA	NA	NA
## IL13	NA	NA	NA	NA
## NCAM1	NA	NA	-3.683598e-05	NA
## NLRC4	NA	NA	9.252766e-05	NA
## NLRP1	NA	-3.710811e-05	-8.161984e-05	NA
## NLRP2	NA	NA	1.218252e-04	NA
## NOD2	NA	-3.507227e-04	-4.839517e-04	NA
## PTPRCv1	NA	-4.291627e-06	NA	NA
## RAB13	NA	NA	NA	NA
## STAT2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TAP2	NA	-7.121801e-05	NA	NA
## TGFB1	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TLR4	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TLR6	NA	-1.771751e-04	-2.000088e-04	NA
## TLR7	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TLR8	NA	-1.082098e-06	-1.503575e-05	NA
## TNIP1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	Biomarker02	Patient.Biomarker02	Patient00.E	Biomarker00.E
## (Intercept)	2.351863e+00	1.157042e+01	4.96724526	6.112037e-01
## Age	NA	-3.428147e-02	-0.01863679	NA
## Alcoholpast6months	NA	-1.608607e-01	-0.63923515	NA
## BMI	NA	-2.430057e-01	NA	NA
## Gender	NA	-8.761654e-01	-0.34686568	NA
## Cough.2weeks	NA	-5.953415e-01	NA	NA
## Fever	NA	3.370288e-01	NA	NA
## PrevdiaqTB	NA	NA	-0.88383745	NA
## Severethinness	NA	-8.243340e-01	NA	NA
## Tobaccolast6months	NA	-1.693903e+00	-0.36204238	NA
## ABR	NA	NA	NA	NA
## AIRE	NA	NA	NA	NA
## B2M	NA	NA	NA	NA
## BCL2	NA	-8.228337e-06	NA	NA
## CASP8	NA	NA	NA	NA

## CCL4	NA	NA	NA	-2.757538e-05
## CD14	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CD19	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CD3E	-6.223551e-05	NA	NA	NA
## CTLA4	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CXCL10	-1.013848e-03	-1.701927e-03	NA	NA
## CXCL13	NA	NA	NA	NA
## DSE	NA	NA	NA	NA
## GBP2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## GNLY	NA	NA	NA	NA
## IL13	2.078432e-04	4.595590e-04	NA	NA
## NCAM1	NA	NA	NA	NA
## NLRC4	NA	NA	NA	NA
## NLRP1	NA	NA	NA	NA
## NLRP2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## NOD2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## PTPRCv1	NA	NA	NA	NA
## RAB13	NA	NA	NA	NA
## STAT2	NA	-2.198483e-04	NA	NA
## TAP2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TGFB1	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TLR4	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TLR6	-7.561992e-04	-1.378282e-03	NA	NA
## TLR7	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TLR8	-2.058315e-05	-5.226969e-08	NA	NA
## TNIP1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	Patient.Biomarker00.E			
## (Intercept)	8.325792e+00			
## Age	-2.768834e-02			
## Alcoholpast6months	-1.033800e+00			
## BMI	NA			
## Gender	-4.980854e-01			
## Cough.2weeks	NA			
## Fever	NA			
## PrevdiagTB	-1.915160e+00			
## Severethinness	NA			
## Tobaccolast6months	-1.150044e-01			
## ABR	-1.998357e-04			
## AIRE	NA			
## B2M	1.093422e-05			
## BCL2	NA			
## CASP8	3.227960e-05			
## CCL4	NA			
## CD14	1.129890e-04			
## CD19	NA			
## CD3E	NA			
## CTLA4	6.366240e-04			
## CXCL10	-1.111306e-03			
## CXCL13	NA			
## DSE	-8.576758e-04			
## GBP2	-1.712228e-05			
## GNLY	-1.982063e-05			
## IL13	NA			
## NCAM1	NA			

```

## NLRC4          1.979446e-03
## NLRP1          NA
## NLRP2          NA
## NOD2           NA
## PTPRCv1       NA
## RAB13         -5.528098e-04
## STAT2         NA
## TAP2          NA
## TGFB1         -3.405436e-05
## TLR4          -5.711420e-04
## TLR6          NA
## TLR7          1.118689e-03
## TLR8          NA
## TNIP1         -5.144031e-04

```

```
combinedMat.02XX[-c(1:10), ] <- 1000*combinedMat.02XX[-c(1:10), ]
```

```
combinedMat.02XX
```

##	Patient00	Biomarker00	Patient.Biomarker00	Patient02
## (Intercept)	1.119987416	1.360444703	2.624836859	3.18672402
## Age	-0.002848961	NA	NA	-0.00414461
## Alcoholpast6months	-0.438961554	NA	-0.252174111	-0.32204999
## BMI	NA	NA	NA	-0.16414879
## Gender	-0.929178034	NA	-0.589881813	-0.39897567
## Cough.2weeks	NA	NA	NA	NA
## Fever	NA	NA	NA	NA
## Prevdia TB	-0.409437200	NA	-0.252672751	-0.29770279
## Severethinness	-0.841756922	NA	-0.538495757	-0.27184624
## Tobaccolast6months	-0.572536506	NA	-0.356023334	-0.55553903
## ABR	NA	NA	NA	NA
## AIRE	NA	-0.889829547	-1.537901184	NA
## B2M	NA	NA	0.000266098	NA
## BCL2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CASP8	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CCL4	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CD14	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CD19	NA	-0.366762280	-0.457290624	NA
## CD3E	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CTLA4	NA	NA	NA	NA
## CXCL10	NA	NA	-0.076121167	NA
## CXCL13	NA	-0.093572383	-0.184706913	NA
## DSE	NA	NA	NA	NA
## GBP2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## GNLY	NA	NA	NA	NA
## IL13	NA	NA	NA	NA
## NCAM1	NA	NA	-0.036835976	NA
## NLRC4	NA	NA	0.092527662	NA
## NLRP1	NA	-0.037108109	-0.081619837	NA
## NLRP2	NA	NA	0.121825155	NA
## NOD2	NA	-0.350722739	-0.483951698	NA
## PTPRCv1	NA	-0.004291627	NA	NA
## RAB13	NA	NA	NA	NA
## STAT2	NA	NA	NA	NA
## TAP2	NA	-0.071218010	NA	NA

##	TGFB1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	TLR4	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	TLR6	NA	-0.177175062	-0.200008751	NA
##	TLR7	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	TLR8	NA	-0.001082098	-0.015035747	NA
##	TNIP1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##		Biomarker02	Patient.Biomarker02	Patient00.E	Biomarker00.E
##	(Intercept)	2.35186322	1.157042e+01	4.96724526	0.61120374
##	Age	NA	-3.428147e-02	-0.01863679	NA
##	Alcoholpast6months	NA	-1.608607e-01	-0.63923515	NA
##	BMI	NA	-2.430057e-01	NA	NA
##	Gender	NA	-8.761654e-01	-0.34686568	NA
##	Cough.2weeks	NA	-5.953415e-01	NA	NA
##	Fever	NA	3.370288e-01	NA	NA
##	PrevdiagTB	NA	NA	-0.88383745	NA
##	Severethinness	NA	-8.243340e-01	NA	NA
##	Tobaccolast6months	NA	-1.693903e+00	-0.36204238	NA
##	ABR	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	AIRE	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	B2M	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	BCL2	NA	-8.228337e-03	NA	NA
##	CASP8	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	CCL4	NA	NA	NA	-0.02757538
##	CD14	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	CD19	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	CD3E	-0.06223551	NA	NA	NA
##	CTLA4	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	CXCL10	-1.01384792	-1.701927e+00	NA	NA
##	CXCL13	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	DSE	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	GBP2	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	GNLY	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	IL13	0.20784315	4.595590e-01	NA	NA
##	NCAM1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	NLRC4	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	NLRP1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	NLRP2	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	NOD2	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	PTPRCv1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	RAB13	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	STAT2	NA	-2.198483e-01	NA	NA
##	TAP2	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	TGFB1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	TLR4	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	TLR6	-0.75619915	-1.378282e+00	NA	NA
##	TLR7	NA	NA	NA	NA
##	TLR8	-0.02058315	-5.226969e-05	NA	NA
##	TNIP1	NA	NA	NA	NA
##		Patient.Biomarker00.E			
##	(Intercept)		8.32579240		
##	Age		-0.02768834		
##	Alcoholpast6months		-1.03380015		
##	BMI		NA		
##	Gender		-0.49808541		

```

## Cough.2weeks          NA
## Fever                 NA
## PrevdiagTB           -1.91516004
## Severethinness       NA
## Tobaccolast6months  -0.11500436
## ABR                   -0.19983575
## AIRE                  NA
## B2M                   0.01093422
## BCL2                  NA
## CASP8                 0.03227960
## CCL4                  NA
## CD14                  0.11298905
## CD19                  NA
## CD3E                  NA
## CTLA4                 0.63662399
## CXCL10                -1.11130646
## CXCL13                NA
## DSE                   -0.85767578
## GBP2                  -0.01712228
## GNLY                  -0.01982063
## IL13                  NA
## NCAM1                 NA
## NLRC4                 1.97944640
## NLRP1                 NA
## NLRP2                 NA
## NOD2                  NA
## PTPRCv1               NA
## RAB13                 -0.55280976
## STAT2                 NA
## TAP2                  NA
## TGFB1                 -0.03405436
## TLR4                  -0.57114201
## TLR6                  NA
## TLR7                  1.11868886
## TLR8                  NA
## TNIP1                 -0.51440306

```

```

print(xtable(combinedMat.02XX, digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/combin

```

Data for Figure 4, panel A

```

cbind(lassoTrainResults00.early.1b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
      lassoTrainResults00.early.0b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
      lassoTrainResults00.early.2b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")])

```

##		truth	X1	truth	X1	truth
## 1	Early Responders	0.745379307	Early Responders	0.4610200	Early Responders	
## 2	Early Responders	0.486176918	Early Responders	0.4795889	Early Responders	
## 3	Early Responders	0.268856960	Early Responders	0.3097493	Early Responders	
## 4	Early Responders	0.069426793	Early Responders	0.3883090	Early Responders	
## 5	Early Responders	0.608371194	Early Responders	0.7876738	Early Responders	
## 6	Early Responders	0.400427371	Early Responders	0.5493047	Early Responders	
## 7	Early Responders	0.025748939	Early Responders	0.4397473	Early Responders	
## 8	Early Responders	0.682076941	Early Responders	0.8090334	Early Responders	

## 9	Early Responders	0.410564297	Early Responders	0.5858793	Early Responders
## 10	Early Responders	0.385838327	Early Responders	0.5206248	Early Responders
## 11	Early Responders	0.517534253	Early Responders	0.6978535	Early Responders
## 12	Early Responders	0.243582209	Early Responders	0.4333840	Early Responders
## 13	Early Responders	0.429223181	Early Responders	0.5438285	Early Responders
## 14	Early Responders	0.269361362	Early Responders	0.4656541	Early Responders
## 15	Early Responders	0.195838796	Early Responders	0.6225765	Early Responders
## 16	Early Responders	0.707491600	Early Responders	0.7478765	Early Responders
## 17	Early Responders	0.423610231	Early Responders	0.5722522	Early Responders
## 18	Early Responders	0.407882399	Early Responders	0.4769206	Early Responders
## 19	Early Responders	0.504369172	Early Responders	0.5696326	Early Responders
## 20	Early Responders	0.064793414	Early Responders	0.4106590	Early Responders
## 21	Early Responders	0.278820074	Early Responders	0.5696326	Early Responders
## 22	Early Responders	0.161610466	Early Responders	0.4537409	Early Responders
## 23	Early Responders	0.182232286	Early Responders	0.4517727	Early Responders
## 24	Early Responders	0.144005895	Early Responders	0.5948929	Early Responders
## 25	Early Responders	0.009076086	Early Responders	0.5000227	Early Responders
## 26	Early Responders	0.261830115	Early Responders	0.7054183	Early Responders
## 27	Early Responders	0.556864849	Early Responders	0.6377215	Early Responders
## 28	Early Responders	0.112303706	Early Responders	0.5690542	Early Responders
## 29	Early Responders	0.332843705	Early Responders	0.5186508	Early Responders
## 30	Early Responders	0.366421930	Early Responders	0.6783659	Early Responders
## 31	Early Responders	0.324547061	Early Responders	0.7443462	Early Responders
## 32	Early Responders	0.419346377	Early Responders	0.7335622	Early Responders
## 33	Non Responders	0.826554315	Non Responders	0.7076355	Non Responders
## 34	Non Responders	0.643367211	Non Responders	0.7111449	Non Responders
## 35	Non Responders	0.835394049	Non Responders	0.7407836	Non Responders
## 36	Non Responders	0.989283627	Non Responders	0.8506326	Non Responders
## 37	Non Responders	0.741063161	Non Responders	0.6277627	Non Responders
## 38	Non Responders	0.795797223	Non Responders	0.3944713	Non Responders
## 39	Non Responders	0.808793859	Non Responders	0.6444700	Non Responders
## 40	Non Responders	0.859812852	Non Responders	0.6824110	Non Responders
## 41	Non Responders	0.780349081	Non Responders	0.5813504	Non Responders
## 42	Non Responders	0.701292276	Non Responders	0.6030149	Non Responders
## 43	Non Responders	0.772317518	Non Responders	0.5028735	Non Responders
## 44	Non Responders	0.817148770	Non Responders	0.8910599	Non Responders
## 45	Non Responders	0.968151158	Non Responders	0.8143695	Non Responders
## 46	Non Responders	0.832768944	Non Responders	0.5028735	Non Responders
## 47	Non Responders	0.691679363	Non Responders	0.5696326	Non Responders
## 48	Non Responders	0.840536089	Non Responders	0.7898427	Non Responders
## 49	Non Responders	0.508824762	Non Responders	0.7022621	Non Responders
## 50	Non Responders	0.896669501	Non Responders	0.8211081	Non Responders
## 51	Non Responders	0.692474772	Non Responders	0.6795831	Non Responders
## 52	Non Responders	0.818317805	Non Responders	0.7335622	Non Responders
## 53	Non Responders	0.973592755	Non Responders	0.7338775	Non Responders
## 54	Non Responders	0.472761302	Non Responders	0.5234789	Non Responders
## 55	Non Responders	0.724709973	Non Responders	0.5252829	Non Responders
## 56	Non Responders	0.565218265	Non Responders	0.6407236	Non Responders
## 57	Non Responders	0.587296119	Non Responders	0.4795889	Non Responders
## 58	Non Responders	0.851735311	Non Responders	0.8608134	Non Responders
## 59	Non Responders	0.857479611	Non Responders	0.5325908	Non Responders
## 60	Non Responders	0.471609801	Non Responders	0.5354284	Non Responders
## 61	Non Responders	0.904331834	Non Responders	0.5234789	Non Responders
## 62	Non Responders	0.989887990	Non Responders	0.8553068	Non Responders

## 63	Non Responders	0.751080272	Non Responders	0.6783659	Non Responders
## 64	Non Responders	0.933553328	Non Responders	0.7683717	Non Responders
## 65	Non Responders	0.629791274	Non Responders	0.7683717	Non Responders
## 66	Non Responders	0.849583914	Non Responders	0.8127476	Non Responders
## 67	Non Responders	0.939071670	Non Responders	0.7720812	Non Responders
## 68	Non Responders	0.950290446	Non Responders	0.8070087	Non Responders
## 69	Non Responders	0.880492997	Non Responders	0.8358613	Non Responders
## 70	Non Responders	0.942712114	Non Responders	0.5985451	Non Responders
## 71	Non Responders	0.981680924	Non Responders	0.8652195	Non Responders
## 72	Non Responders	0.866608878	Non Responders	0.7017686	Non Responders
## 73	Non Responders	0.949659756	Non Responders	0.7548396	Non Responders
## 74	Non Responders	0.854581474	Non Responders	0.7266758	Non Responders
## 75	Non Responders	0.902268364	Non Responders	0.7968741	Non Responders
## 76	Non Responders	0.985251702	Non Responders	0.8797212	Non Responders
## 77	Non Responders	0.915818345	Non Responders	0.7335622	Non Responders
## 78	Non Responders	0.846511255	Non Responders	0.6824186	Non Responders
## 79	Non Responders	0.886928787	Non Responders	0.7938407	Non Responders
## 80	Non Responders	0.538706747	Non Responders	0.7443462	Non Responders
## 81	Non Responders	0.762824683	Non Responders	0.4795889	Non Responders
## 82	Non Responders	0.685082936	Non Responders	0.7781667	Non Responders
## 83	Non Responders	0.647364202	Non Responders	0.5923132	Non Responders
## 84	Non Responders	0.900666077	Non Responders	0.7266758	Non Responders
## 85	Non Responders	0.966064466	Non Responders	0.6589621	Non Responders
## 86	Non Responders	0.843818970	Non Responders	0.7749390	Non Responders
## 87	Non Responders	0.832021438	Non Responders	0.5374037	Non Responders
## 88	Non Responders	0.946619478	Non Responders	0.6755114	Non Responders
## 89	Non Responders	0.766651071	Non Responders	0.6778510	Non Responders
## 90	Non Responders	0.828617676	Non Responders	0.5878052	Non Responders
##	X1				
## 1		0.6463644			
## 2		0.6444965			
## 3		0.6441489			
## 4		0.6417244			
## 5		0.6446102			
## 6		0.6461312			
## 7		0.6368918			
## 8		0.6449450			
## 9		0.6458979			
## 10		0.6441679			
## 11		0.6424911			
## 12		0.6451786			
## 13		0.6469567			
## 14		0.6448376			
## 15		0.6420857			
## 16		0.6434280			
## 17		0.6457023			
## 18		0.6449892			
## 19		0.6443259			
## 20		0.6442690			
## 21		0.6439846			
## 22		0.6436051			
## 23		0.6426748			
## 24		0.6441300			
## 25		0.6416229			

26 0.6427318
27 0.6431306
28 0.6431116
29 0.6444017
30 0.6449765
31 0.6429977
32 0.6424658
33 0.6456140
34 0.6431180
35 0.6449765
36 0.6453111
37 0.6457780
38 0.6447997
39 0.6450902
40 0.6444459
41 0.6431876
42 0.6445470
43 0.6452669
44 0.6434154
45 0.6452985
46 0.6408363
47 0.6457023
48 0.6444523
49 0.6445597
50 0.6436937
51 0.6446102
52 0.6460807
53 0.6469567
54 0.6431623
55 0.6451028
56 0.6435039
57 0.6441300
58 0.6438644
59 0.6459862
60 0.6450712
61 0.6448250
62 0.6429534
63 0.6449955
64 0.6459862
65 0.6444017
66 0.6446418
67 0.6454689
68 0.6442880
69 0.6439213
70 0.6453932
71 0.6455131
72 0.6444333
73 0.6456582
74 0.6448881
75 0.6435419
76 0.6458411
77 0.6469567
78 0.6454121
79 0.6434660

```
## 80 0.6445597
## 81 0.6446797
## 82 0.6435988
## 83 0.6456203
## 84 0.6438328
## 85 0.6448818
## 86 0.6469567
## 87 0.6452101
## 88 0.6447618
## 89 0.6443196
## 90 0.6469567
```

```
print(xtable(cbind(lassoTrainResults00.early.1b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
                  lassoTrainResults00.early.0b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
                  lassoTrainResults00.early.2b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")]),
      digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/fig4p
```

Making ROC curves

```
plot(rocObj.00.early.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.00.early.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.00.early.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.77", "Markers only: 0.67", "Basic + Markers: 0.97"),
      lty = 1:3, bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)
```



```

plot(smooth(rocObj.00.early.1), xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(smooth(rocObj.00.early.0), add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(smooth(rocObj.00.early.2), add = TRUE, lty = 3)

```


Solid line: both basic characteristics and markers. Dashed line: basic characteristics only. Dotted line: markers only.

```
pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/roc00earlyv1.pdf")
```

```

plot(rocObj.00.early.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.00.early.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.00.early.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.77", "Markers only: 0.67", "Basic + Markers: 0.97"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

dev.off()

```

```
pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision//prob00v1.pdf")
```

```

plot(1-X1 ~ factor(truth, exclude = NULL), data = lassoTrainResults00.1b[["pred"]],
     xlab = "Groups",
     ylab = "Predicted probability of cure")

```

```
dev.off()
```

Early responders - prediction at 2 months

```
train.02.early.1 <- cbind(visit2.early.data[, 1:13], visit2.early.data[, rownames(resultsMat.early.2a)])
```

```
head(train.02.early.1)
```

```
##      PID Sample.ID      Donor      Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks Fever
## 1  20400 IPAX1684 Early Responders Training 54      1      1      2
## 2  260100 IPAX0584 Early Responders Training 50      1      1      2
## 3  360100 IPAX0608 Early Responders Training 70      2      1      1
## 4 1050100 IPAX0667 Early Responders Training 29      1      1      2
## 5 1380100 IPAX0257 Early Responders Training 35      1      1      2
## 6 1790100 IPAX0731 Early Responders Training 70      2      2      2
##      PrevdiagTB Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months      BMI Severethinness NCAM1
## 1      2      2      2      2 16.21      2      200
## 2      2      2      2      2 17.99      2      401
## 3      2      2      2      2 12.20      1      264
## 4      2      1      1      1 16.71      2      283
## 5      2      2      2      2 19.13      2      297
## 6      1      2      2      2 20.56      2      393
##      CTLA4 BCL2 RAB13 GZMA  GNLV GZMB  PRF1 PTPRCv1 CCL4 TLR6 IFI44 IFIT5 IFIH1
## 1  900  602  200 1138 18892 2177  3409  1352  200 2813  6311  5351  3235
## 2 1391  542  483  631 18485 2874  5108  2736  584 3982  1076  3460  1848
## 3  981  651  200  637 18645 3071  5143  2373  540 2184  2763  3827  2102
## 4 1052 1717  663 1366 33318 5309  8349  5207  648 5041  8983 11787  4265
## 5 1298  489  275 2172 50319 7438 12718  4130  671 2819  1704  8450  2519
## 6 1445 1274  745 4031 78644 9689  8874  5047  798 1774  1828  7134  1585
##      IFI44L OAS2 OAS3 STAT2 VEGF
## 1  5671  200 1929  2091  200
## 2  1080  200 1170  1279  200
## 3  2947  807 2314  1665  200
## 4  9350 1831 5488  2652  444
## 5  1807  200 1087  1639  200
## 6  1103  200  825  1283  200
```

```
dim(train.02.early.1)
```

```
## [1] 67 32
```

P

Fitting a LASSO logistic regression model only using basic participant characteristics (no marker data, only information about age, gender, cough (past 2 weeks), fever, previous diagnosed TB, tobacco (last 6 months), alcohol (past 6 months), BMI, and severe thinness):

```
set.seed(201907024)
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.0a <- lassoTrain(train.02.early.1[, c(5:13)],
                                          train.02.early.1[, 3], skipVar = 1:10)
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.0a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 10 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
```

```
##      1 1
```

```
## (Intercept)      6.28517898 NA
## Age              -0.02921828 NA
## Gender           -0.05767835 NA
## Cough.2weeks     0.00000000 NA
## Fever            0.00000000 NA
## PrevdiagTB      -1.32668274 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.41984620 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.28815653 NA
## BMI              0.00000000 NA
## Severethinness  -0.51408300 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.0a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 7 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##              1  1
## (Intercept)  6.28517898 NA
## Age          -0.02921828 NA
## Gender       -0.05767835 NA
## PrevdiagTB  -1.32668274 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.41984620 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.28815653 NA
## Severethinness -0.51408300 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.0b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults02.early.0a,
                                                train.02.early.1[, c(5:13)], train.02.early.1[, 3],
                                                "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
```

```
rocObj.02.early.0 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.early.0b[["pred"]])
rocObj.02.early.0
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.early.0b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 23 controls (truth Early Responders) < 44 cases (truth Non Responders).
## Area under the curve: 0.7935
```

```
ci(rocObj.02.early.0, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.686-0.9009 (DeLong)
```

```
#aucMat.early <- matrix(NA, 3, 9)
aucMat.early[1, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.00.early.0, of = "auc")
```

B+P

Fitting LASSO to basic participant characteristics and the selection of identified biomarkers (from step 1) using the criterion p-value less than 0.05:

```
set.seed(201907025)
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.1a <- lassoTrain(train.02.early.1[, -c(1:4)],
                                         train.02.early.1[, 3], skipVar = 1:10)
lassoTrainResults02.early.1a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 29 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##              1  1
```

```

## (Intercept)      7.315960e+00 NA
## Age             -3.152424e-02 NA
## Gender          .           NA
## Cough.2weeks    .           NA
## Fever          .           NA
## PrevdiagTB      -9.949861e-01 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -5.824221e-01 NA
## Alcoholpast6months .         NA
## BMI             .           NA
## Severethinness  -1.700203e-01 NA
## NCAM1          .           .
## CTLA4          .           .
## BCL2           .           .
## RAB13          .           .
## GZMA           -3.938565e-05  1
## GNLY           -3.198118e-05  1
## GZMB          .           .
## PRF1          .           .
## PTPRCv1       .           .
## CCL4          .           .
## TLR6          -4.969538e-04  14
## IFI44         .           .
## IFIT5         .           .
## IFIH1         .           .
## IFI44L        .           .
## OAS2          -8.427879e-05  2
## OAS3          -1.205646e-04  3
## STAT2         .           .
## VEGF          2.746353e-03  78

```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.1a[["red.coef"]]
```

```

## 11 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##              1  1
## (Intercept)  7.315960e+00 NA
## Age         -3.152424e-02 NA
## PrevdiagTB  -9.949861e-01 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -5.824221e-01 NA
## Severethinness -1.700203e-01 NA
## GZMA        -3.938565e-05  1
## GNLY        -3.198118e-05  1
## TLR6        -4.969538e-04  14
## OAS2        -8.427879e-05  2
## OAS3        -1.205646e-04  3
## VEGF        2.746353e-03  78

```

```

lassoTrainResults02.early.1b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults02.early.1a,
                                              train.02.early.1[, -c(1:4)], train.02.early.1[, 3],
                                              "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")

```

```

rocObj.02.early.1 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.early.1b[["pred"]])
rocObj.02.early.1

```

```

##
## Call:

```

```
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.early.1b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 23 controls (truth Early Responders) < 44 cases (truth Non Responders).
## Area under the curve: 0.918
```

```
ci(rocObj.02.early.1, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.8554-0.9806 (DeLong)
```

B

Fitting LASSO to selection of identified biomarkers without the basic participant characteristics:

```
set.seed(201907026)
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.2a <- lassoTrain(train.02.early.1[, -c(1:13)],
                                          train.02.early.1[, 3])
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.2a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 20 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
```

```
##           1  1
## (Intercept) 3.203436e+00 NA
## NCAM1      .      .
## CTLA4      .      .
## BCL2       .      .
## RAB13      .      .
## GZMA       -8.206521e-06  0
## GNLY       -2.245253e-05  0
## GZMB       -8.853922e-05  2
## PRF1       .      .
## PTPRCv1    .      .
## CCL4       .      .
## TLR6       -6.474326e-04 14
## IFI44      .      .
## IFIT5      .      .
## IFIH1      .      .
## IFI44L     .      .
## OAS2       .      .
## OAS3       -9.629167e-05  2
## STAT2      .      .
## VEGF       3.650003e-03  81
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.2a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 7 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
```

```
##           1  1
## (Intercept) 3.203436e+00 NA
## GZMA       -8.206521e-06  0
## GNLY       -2.245253e-05  0
## GZMB       -8.853922e-05  2
## TLR6       -6.474326e-04 14
## OAS3       -9.629167e-05  2
## VEGF       3.650003e-03  81
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.early.2b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults02.early.2a,
                                                train.02.early.1[, -c(1:13)], train.02.early.1[, 3],
```

```

"TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")

rocObj.02.early.2 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.early.2b[["pred"]])
rocObj.02.early.2

##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.early.2b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 23 controls (truth Early Responders) < 44 cases (truth Non Responders).
## Area under the curve: 0.8439
ci(rocObj.02.early.2, of = "auc")

## 95% CI: 0.7469-0.9408 (DeLong)
list.02.early <- list(
  Basic = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.early.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  BasicMarker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.early.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE]
  Marker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.early.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE])

idx.02.early <- Reduce(union, lapply(list.02.early, rownames))

combinedMat.02.early <- do.call(cbind, lapply(list.02.early, "[", idx.02.early, ))
# code modified after:
# https://stackoverflow.com/questions/16808269/combine-data-frames-in-r-using-only-common-row-names
rownames(combinedMat.02.early) <- idx.02.early
combinedMat.02.early

##
## Basic BasicMarker Marker
## (Intercept) 6.28517898 7.315960e+00 3.203436e+00
## Age -0.02921828 -3.152424e-02 NA
## Gender -0.05767835 NA NA
## PrevdiagTB -1.32668274 -9.949861e-01 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.41984620 -5.824221e-01 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.28815653 NA NA
## Severethinness -0.51408300 -1.700203e-01 NA
## GZMA NA -3.938565e-05 -8.206521e-06
## GNLY NA -3.198118e-05 -2.245253e-05
## TLR6 NA -4.969538e-04 -6.474326e-04
## OAS2 NA -8.427879e-05 NA
## OAS3 NA -1.205646e-04 -9.629167e-05
## VEGF NA 2.746353e-03 3.650003e-03
## GZMB NA NA -8.853922e-05

combinedMat.02.early[-c(1:7), ] <- 1000*combinedMat.02.early[-c(1:7), ]

combined.02.early.mark <- combinedMat.02.early[-c(1:7), ]
combined.02.early.mark <- combined.02.early.mark[order(row.names(combined.02.early.mark)), ]
combinedMat.02.early <- rbind(combinedMat.02.early[1:7, ], combined.02.early.mark)
combinedMat.02.early

##
## Basic BasicMarker Marker
## (Intercept) 6.28517898 7.31595992 3.203435899
## Age -0.02921828 -0.03152424 NA
## Gender -0.05767835 NA NA

```

```
## PrevdiagTB          -1.32668274 -0.99498611          NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.41984620 -0.58242211          NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.28815653           NA          NA
## Severethinness     -0.51408300 -0.17002033          NA
## GNLY               NA -0.03198118 -0.022452533
## GZMA               NA -0.03938565 -0.008206521
## GZMB               NA           NA -0.088539224
## OAS2               NA -0.08427879           NA
## OAS3               NA -0.12056462 -0.096291668
## TLR6               NA -0.49695376 -0.647432609
## VEGF               NA  2.74635281  3.650002762
```

```
print(xtable(combinedMat.00.early, digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/combin
```

Making ROC curves

```
plot(rocObj.02.early.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")
```

```
plot(rocObj.02.early.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)
```

```
plot(rocObj.02.early.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)
```

```
legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.79", "Markers only: 0.85", "Basic + Markers: 0.92"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)
```



```
plot(smooth(rocObj.02.early.1), xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")
```

```
plot(smooth(rocObj.02.early.0), add = TRUE, lty = 2)
```

```
plot(smooth(rocObj.02.early.2), add = TRUE, lty = 3)
```


Solid line: both basic characteristics and markers. Dashed line: basic characteristics only. Dotted line: markers only.

```
pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/roc02earlyv1.pdf")
```

```
plot(rocObj.02.early.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")
```

```
plot(rocObj.02.early.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)
```

```
plot(rocObj.02.early.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)
```

```
legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.79", "Markers only: 0.85", "Basic + Markers: 0.92"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)
```

```
dev.off()
```

Protein markers

Importing the data:

```
baseline.prot.data <- read.csv("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/baseline.prot.data")
```

```
head(baseline.prot.data)
```

```
##      PID  SampleID  Donor  Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks  Fever  PrevdiagTB
## 1  20400  IQFT141311  TB Cures Training  54      1      1      1      2
```

```
## 2 260100 IQFT030411 TB Cures Training 50 1 1 1 2
## 3 360100 IQFT031411 TB Cures Training 70 2 1 1 2
## 4 950100 IQFT074911 TB Cures Training 70 1 1 1 2
## 5 1050100 IQFT040111 TB Cures Training 29 1 1 2 2
## 6 1380100 IQFT008710 TB Cures Training 35 1 1 1 2
## Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months BMI Severethinness IFNg IL10
## 1 2 2 16.99 2 122.63 1.08
## 2 2 2 17.99 2 323.34 2.43
## 3 2 2 13.14 1 735.69 34.40
## 4 2 2 17.61 2 399.72 2.28
## 5 1 1 15.98 1 1100.52 11.22
## 6 2 2 16.48 2 51.88 4.35
## IL12p70 IL1b IL4 TNFa GMCSF IL15 IL17A IL5 IL7 VEGF Eotaxin3
## 1 0.17 691.72 0.04 424.57 18.12 5.09 1.40 0.16 13.54 479.68 400.63
## 2 0.58 712.30 0.28 582.69 7.87 2.41 2.26 5.35 10.61 98.05 93.67
## 3 1.43 1506.53 0.29 3668.05 124.18 3.55 0.55 0.25 21.05 260.90 607.76
## 4 0.20 733.73 0.19 400.10 14.67 1.53 0.57 0.93 9.77 281.79 254.21
## 5 0.31 678.66 0.24 588.96 4.54 2.37 0.30 0.51 14.96 2.14 99.75
## 6 0.30 1149.28 0.29 228.11 2.18 4.03 1.88 0.94 21.30 677.00 286.55
## IL8 IP10 MCP1 MDC MIP1b
## 1 32805.87 2734.65 16639.61 795.84 4253.43
## 2 64548.92 10868.44 25414.82 1338.10 11309.51
## 3 159617.58 16329.52 29705.85 1716.89 21394.59
## 4 32081.60 6703.45 19376.37 1751.86 5217.44
## 5 101965.91 25537.52 20446.35 1781.05 10217.95
## 6 640057.14 1164.40 11385.79 1888.89 12829.33
```

```
dim(baseline.prot.data)
```

```
## [1] 83 31
```

```
visit1.prot.data <- read.csv("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment")
```

```
head(visit1.prot.data)
```

```
## PID SampleID Donor Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks Fever PrevdiagTB
## 1 260100 IQFT048311 TB Cures Training 50 1 2 2 2
## 2 360100 IQFT048411 TB Cures Training 70 2 1 1 2
## 3 950100 IQFT085011 TB Cures Training 70 1 2 2 2
## 4 1380100 IQFT019210 TB Cures Training 35 1 1 1 2
## 5 1790100 IQFT056111 TB Cures Training 70 2 2 2 1
## 6 2040100 IQFT051611 TB Cures Training 35 1 1 2 2
## Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months BMI Severethinness IFNg IL10
## 1 2 2 17.82 2 180.82 1.08
## 2 2 2 11.96 1 129.59 1.83
## 3 1 2 17.80 2 724.97 2.70
## 4 2 2 19.13 2 102.29 0.76
## 5 2 2 20.56 2 902.85 1.21
## 6 2 1 16.49 2 3088.37 0.86
## IL12p70 IL1b IL4 TNFa GMCSF IL15 IL17A IL5 IL7 VEGF Eotaxin3
## 1 0.14 511.20 0.39 640.12 6.24 2.55 2.39 2.94 11.12 437.17 276.25
## 2 0.10 158.85 0.02 262.88 2.09 2.82 0.72 1.74 7.32 134.91 673.86
## 3 0.65 1170.72 0.48 756.22 32.32 1.68 1.63 3.28 10.23 177.47 642.66
## 4 0.90 3138.52 0.49 211.51 28.58 2.31 22.97 1.30 19.60 481.28 2034.48
## 5 0.17 192.98 0.48 60.59 4.76 1.29 0.77 2.47 7.55 126.11 298.70
```

```
## 6      0.14  56.82 0.83  40.37  2.10 1.89  1.30 2.75  9.59  18.76  199.45
##          IL8      IP10      MCP1      MDC      MIP1b
## 1  87226.92  3111.18 48761.28 1063.54  5335.24
## 2  50551.63  3393.88 34906.43 1791.59  5075.14
## 3  86353.38 14151.01 77251.73 4380.23 17214.57
## 4 5845020.98 1357.22 52401.45 5042.80 49051.70
## 5  52569.24  6462.96 51318.79 1709.54  2324.71
## 6  25305.20 44315.21 26439.14 2300.43 12136.26
```

```
dim(visit1.prot.data)
```

```
## [1] 56 31
```

```
visit2.prot.data <- read.csv("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment")
```

```
dim(visit2.prot.data)
```

```
## [1] 59 31
```

```
visit6.prot.data <- read.csv("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment")
```

```
dim(visit6.prot.data)
```

```
## [1] 55 31
```

```
visit0.early.prot.data <- read.csv("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment")
```

```
dim(visit0.early.prot.data)
```

```
## [1] 83 31
```

Prediction at baseline

Defining and showing baseline data:

```
train.00.prot.1 <- baseline.prot.data # the entire dataset
```

```
head(train.00.prot.1)
```

```
##      PID  SampleID  Donor      Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks Fever PrevdiagTB
## 1  20400 IQFT141311 TB Cures Training  54      1          1      1      2
## 2  260100 IQFT030411 TB Cures Training  50      1          1      1      2
## 3  360100 IQFT031411 TB Cures Training  70      2          1      1      2
## 4  950100 IQFT074911 TB Cures Training  70      1          1      1      2
## 5 1050100 IQFT040111 TB Cures Training  29      1          1      2      2
## 6 1380100 IQFT008710 TB Cures Training  35      1          1      1      2
##      Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months      BMI Severethinness      IFNg      IL10
## 1              2              2 16.99              2 122.63  1.08
## 2              2              2 17.99              2 323.34  2.43
## 3              2              2 13.14              1 735.69 34.40
## 4              2              2 17.61              2 399.72  2.28
## 5              1              1 15.98              11100.52 11.22
## 6              2              2 16.48              2   51.88  4.35
##      IL12p70      IL1b      IL4      TNFa      GMCSF      IL15      IL17A      IL5      IL7      VEGF      Eotaxin3
## 1  0.17  691.72 0.04  424.57  18.12 5.09  1.40 0.16 13.54 479.68  400.63
## 2  0.58  712.30 0.28  582.69   7.87 2.41  2.26 5.35 10.61  98.05   93.67
## 3  1.43 1506.53 0.29 3668.05 124.18 3.55  0.55 0.25 21.05 260.90  607.76
```

```
## 4 0.20 733.73 0.19 400.10 14.67 1.53 0.57 0.93 9.77 281.79 254.21
## 5 0.31 678.66 0.24 588.96 4.54 2.37 0.30 0.51 14.96 2.14 99.75
## 6 0.30 1149.28 0.29 228.11 2.18 4.03 1.88 0.94 21.30 677.00 286.55
## IL8 IP10 MCP1 MDC MIP1b
## 1 32805.87 2734.65 16639.61 795.84 4253.43
## 2 64548.92 10868.44 25414.82 1338.10 11309.51
## 3 159617.58 16329.52 29705.85 1716.89 21394.59
## 4 32081.60 6703.45 19376.37 1751.86 5217.44
## 5 101965.91 25537.52 20446.35 1781.05 10217.95
## 6 640057.14 1164.40 11385.79 1888.89 12829.33
```

```
dim(train.00.prot.1)
```

```
## [1] 83 31
```

```
names(train.00.prot.1)[14:31]
```

```
## [1] "IFNg" "IL10" "IL12p70" "IL1b" "IL4" "TNFa"
## [7] "GMCSF" "IL15" "IL17A" "IL5" "IL7" "VEGF"
## [13] "Eotaxin3" "IL8" "IP10" "MCP1" "MDC" "MIP1b"
```

```
length(names(train.00.prot.1)[14:31])
```

```
## [1] 18
```

P

Fitting a LASSO logistic regression model only using basic participant characteristics (no marker data, only information about age, gender, cough (past 2 weeks), fever, previous diagnosed TB, tobacco (last 6 months), alcohol (past 6 months), BMI, and severe thinness):

```
set.seed(201907011)
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.prot.0a <- lassoTrain(train.00.prot.1[, c(5:13)], train.00.prot.1[, 3],
                                         skipVar = 1:10)
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.prot.0a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 10 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##                1 1
## (Intercept)    4.559328686 NA
## Age            -0.007040029 NA
## Gender         -0.969723323 NA
## Cough.2weeks   0.000000000 NA
## Fever          0.000000000 NA
## PrevdiagTB    -0.391895879 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.647060236 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.263409467 NA
## BMI           0.000000000 NA
## Severethinness -0.933178239 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.prot.0a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 7 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##                1 1
## (Intercept)    4.559328686 NA
## Age            -0.007040029 NA
## Gender         -0.969723323 NA
## PrevdiagTB    -0.391895879 NA
```

```
## Tobaccolast6months -0.647060236 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.263409467 NA
## Severethinness -0.933178239 NA

lassoTrainResults00.prot.0b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults00.prot.0a,
                                             train.00.prot.1[, c(5:13)], train.00.prot.1[, 3],
                                             "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
rocObj.00.prot.0 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.prot.0b[["pred"]])
rocObj.00.prot.0
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.prot.0b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 49 controls (truth TB Cures) < 34 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.7773
```

```
ci(rocObj.00.prot.0, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.6767-0.878 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.prot <- matrix(NA, 3, 9)
aucMat.prot[1, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.00.prot.0, of = "auc")
```

P+B

Fitting LASSO to basic participant characteristics and the selection of identified biomarkers (from step 1) using the criterion p-value less than 0.05:

```
set.seed(201907012)
lassoTrainResults00.prot.1a <- lassoTrain(train.00.prot.1[, -c(1:4)], train.00.prot.1[, 3],
                                         skipVar = 1:10)
lassoTrainResults00.prot.1a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 28 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##                1  1
## (Intercept)    2.9571466292 NA
## Age            .           NA
## Gender         -0.5714076217 NA
## Cough.2weeks   .           NA
## Fever          .           NA
## PrevdiagTB     -0.4778040420 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.3923779153 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.4249319393 NA
## BMI            .           NA
## Severethinness -0.7195372003 NA
## IFNg           .           .
## IL10           .           .
## IL12p70        .           .
## IL1b           .           .
## IL4            .           .
## TNFa           .           .
## GMCSF          0.0038132121  8
## IL15           .           .
## IL17A          .           .
## IL5           .           .
```

```
## IL7          0.0406383184 91
## VEGF         .          .
## Eotaxin3     0.0002167213 0
## IL8          .          .
## IP10         .          .
## MCP1         .          .
## MDC          -0.0002074590 0
## MIP1b        .          .
lassoTrainResults00.prot.1a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 10 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##                1 1
## (Intercept)    2.9571466292 NA
## Gender         -0.5714076217 NA
## PrevdiagTB     -0.4778040420 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.3923779153 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.4249319393 NA
## Severethinness -0.7195372003 NA
## GMCSF          0.0038132121 8
## IL7            0.0406383184 91
## Eotaxin3       0.0002167213 0
## MDC            -0.0002074590 0
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.prot.1b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults00.prot.1a,
                                              train.00.prot.1[, -c(1:4)], train.00.prot.1[, 3],
                                              "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
```

```
rocObj.00.prot.1 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.prot.1b[["pred"]])
rocObj.00.prot.1
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.prot.1b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 49 controls (truth TB Cures) < 34 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.8271
```

```
ci(rocObj.00.prot.1, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.7378-0.9164 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.prot[2, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.00.prot.1, of = "auc")
```

B

Fitting LASSO to selection of identified biomarkers without the basic participant characteristics:

```
set.seed(201907013)
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.prot.2a <- lassoTrain(train.00.prot.1[, -c(1:13)], train.00.prot.1[, 3])
lassoTrainResults00.prot.2a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 19 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##                1 1
## (Intercept) -0.9129200563 NA
## IFNg         .          .
## IL10         .          .
```

```
## IL12p70 . .
## IL1b . .
## IL4 . .
## TNFa . .
## GMCSF 0.0020843034 4
## IL15 . .
## IL17A . .
## IL5 . .
## IL7 0.0447180963 95
## VEGF . .
## Eotaxin3 . .
## IL8 . .
## IP10 . .
## MCP1 . .
## MDC -0.0001552075 0
## MIP1b . .
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.prot.2a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 4 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##          1 1
## (Intercept) -0.9129200563 NA
## GMCSF 0.0020843034 4
## IL7 0.0447180963 95
## MDC -0.0001552075 0
```

```
lassoTrainResults00.prot.2b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults00.prot.2a,
                                             train.00.prot.1[, -c(1:13)], train.00.prot.1[, 3],
                                             "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
```

```
rocObj.00.prot.2 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.prot.2b[["pred"]])
rocObj.00.prot.2
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults00.prot.2b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 49 controls (truth TB Cures) < 34 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.6915
```

```
ci(rocObj.00.prot.2, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.5716-0.8114 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.prot[3, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.00.prot.2, of = "auc")
```

```
list.00.prot <- list(
  Basic = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.prot.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  BasicMarker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.prot.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Marker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.prot.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE])
```

```
idx.00.prot <- Reduce(union, lapply(list.00.prot, rownames))
```

```
combinedMat.00.prot <- do.call(cbind, lapply(list.00.prot, "[", idx.00.prot, ))
```

```
# code modified after:
```

```
# https://stackoverflow.com/questions/16808269/combine-data-frames-in-r-using-only-common-row-names
```

```
rownames(combinedMat.00.prot) <- idx.00.prot
```

```
combinedMat.00.prot
```

```
##           Basic BasicMarker      Marker
## (Intercept)  4.559328686  2.9571466292 -0.9129200563
## Age          -0.007040029           NA           NA
## Gender       -0.969723323 -0.5714076217           NA
## PrevdiagTB   -0.391895879 -0.4778040420           NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.647060236 -0.3923779153           NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.263409467 -0.4249319393           NA
## Severethinness -0.933178239 -0.7195372003           NA
## GMCSF        NA  0.0038132121  0.0020843034
## IL7          NA  0.0406383184  0.0447180963
## Eotaxin3     NA  0.0002167213           NA
## MDC          NA -0.0002074590 -0.0001552075
```

```
combinedMat.00.prot[-c(1:7), ] <- 1000*combinedMat.00.prot[-c(1:7), ]
```

```
combined.00.prot.mark <- combinedMat.00.prot[-c(1:7), ]
combined.00.prot.mark <- combined.00.prot.mark[order(row.names(combined.00.prot.mark)), ]
combinedMat.00.prot <- rbind(combinedMat.00.prot[1:7, ], combined.00.prot.mark)
combinedMat.00.prot
```

```
##           Basic BasicMarker      Marker
## (Intercept)  4.559328686  2.9571466 -0.9129201
## Age          -0.007040029           NA           NA
## Gender       -0.969723323 -0.5714076           NA
## PrevdiagTB   -0.391895879 -0.4778040           NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.647060236 -0.3923779           NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.263409467 -0.4249319           NA
## Severethinness -0.933178239 -0.7195372           NA
## Eotaxin3     NA  0.2167213           NA
## GMCSF        NA  3.8132121  2.0843034
## IL7          NA  40.6383184  44.7180963
## MDC          NA -0.2074590 -0.1552075
```

```
print(xtable(combinedMat.00, digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/combi")
```

Data for Figure 2, panel C

```
cbind(lassoTrainResults00.prot.1b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
      lassoTrainResults00.prot.0b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
      lassoTrainResults00.prot.2b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")])
```

```
##           truth      X1           truth      X1
## 1          TB Cures 0.2492710          TB Cures 0.22069105
## 2          TB Cures 0.1915947          TB Cures 0.22557228
## 3          TB Cures 0.4034906          TB Cures 0.19610328
## 4          TB Cures 0.1825847          TB Cures 0.20192854
## 5          TB Cures 0.5425638          TB Cures 0.68092041
## 6          TB Cures 0.2498486          TB Cures 0.24455195
## 7          TB Cures 0.2903989          TB Cures 0.47778285
## 8          TB Cures 0.4396006          TB Cures 0.46545890
## 9          TB Cures 0.1795598          TB Cures 0.12432328
## 10         TB Cures 0.2934917          TB Cures 0.29640549
## 11         TB Cures 0.1862735          TB Cures 0.18776075
```

## 12	TB Cures	0.2345590	TB Cures	0.22190422
## 13	TB Cures	0.3952617	TB Cures	0.41319979
## 14	TB Cures	0.4167725	TB Cures	0.43544883
## 15	TB Cures	0.2537000	TB Cures	0.25111336
## 16	TB Cures	0.4668079	TB Cures	0.55130732
## 17	TB Cures	0.4204935	TB Cures	0.35745590
## 18	TB Cures	0.3412218	TB Cures	0.39989422
## 19	TB Cures	0.3359247	TB Cures	0.35745590
## 20	TB Cures	0.2228092	TB Cures	0.31812018
## 21	TB Cures	0.2050478	TB Cures	0.21827899
## 22	TB Cures	0.3138641	TB Cures	0.46896376
## 23	TB Cures	0.2620003	TB Cures	0.24822376
## 24	TB Cures	0.1839954	TB Cures	0.24174600
## 25	TB Cures	0.6331225	TB Cures	0.61689830
## 26	TB Cures	0.2204246	TB Cures	0.46443605
## 27	TB Cures	0.1200372	TB Cures	0.11783162
## 28	TB Cures	0.3109806	TB Cures	0.43371895
## 29	TB Cures	0.5238757	TB Cures	0.42853915
## 30	TB Cures	0.1718448	TB Cures	0.16119134
## 31	TB Cures	0.3400461	TB Cures	0.41822748
## 32	TB Cures	0.3663018	TB Cures	0.43199068
## 33	TB Cures	0.3995089	TB Cures	0.38567290
## 34	TB Cures	0.3145052	TB Cures	0.37873920
## 35	TB Cures	0.1457462	TB Cures	0.09946287
## 36	TB Cures	0.3296127	TB Cures	0.27768094
## 37	TB Cures	0.2685867	TB Cures	0.25377046
## 38	TB Cures	0.2470774	TB Cures	0.39175817
## 39	TB Cures	0.2845466	TB Cures	0.23178070
## 40	TB Cures	0.5124861	TB Cures	0.54525638
## 41	TB Cures	0.3868609	TB Cures	0.36259972
## 42	TB Cures	0.5474967	TB Cures	0.43410912
## 43	TB Cures	0.4951923	TB Cures	0.35745590
## 44	TB Cures	0.3192182	TB Cures	0.34423746
## 45	TB Cures	0.3446531	TB Cures	0.40898025
## 46	TB Cures	0.6833305	TB Cures	0.71022142
## 47	TB Cures	0.4077924	TB Cures	0.42853915
## 48	TB Cures	0.2866466	TB Cures	0.34145347
## 49	TB Cures	0.1957958	TB Cures	0.18350385
## 50	Treatment Failures	0.2914195	Treatment Failures	0.28372308
## 51	Treatment Failures	0.3349022	Treatment Failures	0.42548281
## 52	Treatment Failures	0.5189255	Treatment Failures	0.51897136
## 53	Treatment Failures	0.2272340	Treatment Failures	0.25753350
## 54	Treatment Failures	0.3496753	Treatment Failures	0.24067117
## 55	Treatment Failures	0.6542861	Treatment Failures	0.56865225
## 56	Treatment Failures	0.4176684	Treatment Failures	0.38901421
## 57	Treatment Failures	0.4471763	Treatment Failures	0.62779186
## 58	Treatment Failures	0.6777915	Treatment Failures	0.67167369
## 59	Treatment Failures	0.4178476	Treatment Failures	0.44585970
## 60	Treatment Failures	0.6552801	Treatment Failures	0.70585554
## 61	Treatment Failures	0.7333930	Treatment Failures	0.68130396
## 62	Treatment Failures	0.8187615	Treatment Failures	0.70292374
## 63	Treatment Failures	0.4994857	Treatment Failures	0.60477474
## 64	Treatment Failures	0.5230874	Treatment Failures	0.39008193
## 65	Treatment Failures	0.5287829	Treatment Failures	0.52248531

## 66	Treatment Failures	0.7360778	Treatment Failures	0.51892707
## 67	Treatment Failures	0.7105205	Treatment Failures	0.66543384
## 68	Treatment Failures	0.3647787	Treatment Failures	0.43415271
## 69	Treatment Failures	0.6192846	Treatment Failures	0.68549148
## 70	Treatment Failures	0.7165133	Treatment Failures	0.74506453
## 71	Treatment Failures	0.4806036	Treatment Failures	0.42853915
## 72	Treatment Failures	0.6857235	Treatment Failures	0.40049987
## 73	Treatment Failures	0.6610652	Treatment Failures	0.45981353
## 74	Treatment Failures	0.3567241	Treatment Failures	0.43371895
## 75	Treatment Failures	0.2356824	Treatment Failures	0.22557228
## 76	Treatment Failures	0.7493493	Treatment Failures	0.59434452
## 77	Treatment Failures	0.4475308	Treatment Failures	0.43415271
## 78	Treatment Failures	0.6440961	Treatment Failures	0.62518238
## 79	Treatment Failures	0.3893843	Treatment Failures	0.44934104
## 80	Treatment Failures	0.3356207	Treatment Failures	0.34621838
## 81	Treatment Failures	0.5105499	Treatment Failures	0.63175750
## 82	Treatment Failures	0.5937004	Treatment Failures	0.50837529
## 83	Treatment Failures	0.5502523	Treatment Failures	0.36394938
##	truth	X1		
## 1	TB Cures	0.4029497		
## 2	TB Cures	0.3475693		
## 3	TB Cures	0.5051874		
## 4	TB Cures	0.3279770		
## 5	TB Cures	0.3749810		
## 6	TB Cures	0.4380572		
## 7	TB Cures	0.3078068		
## 8	TB Cures	0.4671378		
## 9	TB Cures	0.3429976		
## 10	TB Cures	0.3604959		
## 11	TB Cures	0.3588737		
## 12	TB Cures	0.3953716		
## 13	TB Cures	0.3172471		
## 14	TB Cures	0.3875817		
## 15	TB Cures	0.4303983		
## 16	TB Cures	0.3823979		
## 17	TB Cures	0.4695223		
## 18	TB Cures	0.3517673		
## 19	TB Cures	0.4103028		
## 20	TB Cures	0.2836195		
## 21	TB Cures	0.3570476		
## 22	TB Cures	0.3336910		
## 23	TB Cures	0.4085492		
## 24	TB Cures	0.2849849		
## 25	TB Cures	0.3831872		
## 26	TB Cures	0.1989592		
## 27	TB Cures	0.3650887		
## 28	TB Cures	0.3045022		
## 29	TB Cures	0.5202196		
## 30	TB Cures	0.2978782		
## 31	TB Cures	0.3188407		
## 32	TB Cures	0.3362875		
## 33	TB Cures	0.3649944		
## 34	TB Cures	0.3807173		
## 35	TB Cures	0.3837080		

```

## 36          TB Cures 0.4211328
## 37          TB Cures 0.4250170
## 38          TB Cures 0.2895047
## 39          TB Cures 0.4353150
## 40          TB Cures 0.3858536
## 41          TB Cures 0.3541150
## 42          TB Cures 0.5696931
## 43          TB Cures 0.6099535
## 44          TB Cures 0.4094529
## 45          TB Cures 0.4488382
## 46          TB Cures 0.3806185
## 47          TB Cures 0.3729807
## 48          TB Cures 0.3616745
## 49          TB Cures 0.3650915
## 50 Treatment Failures 0.3225659
## 51 Treatment Failures 0.3487078
## 52 Treatment Failures 0.3904545
## 53 Treatment Failures 0.3610037
## 54 Treatment Failures 0.5190028
## 55 Treatment Failures 0.5530990
## 56 Treatment Failures 0.3902768
## 57 Treatment Failures 0.3569461
## 58 Treatment Failures 0.4687724
## 59 Treatment Failures 0.3598999
## 60 Treatment Failures 0.3590678
## 61 Treatment Failures 0.5425403
## 62 Treatment Failures 0.5833939
## 63 Treatment Failures 0.2948816
## 64 Treatment Failures 0.4770149
## 65 Treatment Failures 0.4029907
## 66 Treatment Failures 0.6013371
## 67 Treatment Failures 0.5294535
## 68 Treatment Failures 0.3302211
## 69 Treatment Failures 0.4128987
## 70 Treatment Failures 0.4581119
## 71 Treatment Failures 0.4697303
## 72 Treatment Failures 0.5889842
## 73 Treatment Failures 0.6881071
## 74 Treatment Failures 0.3487199
## 75 Treatment Failures 0.3996648
## 76 Treatment Failures 0.6475639
## 77 Treatment Failures 0.4407450
## 78 Treatment Failures 0.4812265
## 79 Treatment Failures 0.3866585
## 80 Treatment Failures 0.4210316
## 81 Treatment Failures 0.3225322
## 82 Treatment Failures 0.5058716
## 83 Treatment Failures 0.5063859

```

```

print(xtable(cbind(lassoTrainResults00.prot.1b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
                  lassoTrainResults00.prot.0b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
                  lassoTrainResults00.prot.2b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")]),
      digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumarán/2018-TB treatment/revision/fig2p

```

Making ROC curves

```
plot(rocObj.00.prot.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.00.prot.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.00.prot.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.78", "Markers only: 0.69", "Basic + Markers: 0.83"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)
```



```
plot(smooth(rocObj.00.prot.1), xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(smooth(rocObj.00.prot.0), add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(smooth(rocObj.00.prot.2), add = TRUE, lty = 3)
```


Solid line: both basic characteristics and markers. Dashed line: basic characteristics only. Dotted line: markers only.

```
pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/roc00protv1.pdf")
plot(rocObj.00.prot.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.00.prot.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.00.prot.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.78", "Markers only: 0.69", "Basic + Markers: 0.83"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

dev.off()

pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/prob00v1.pdf")

plot(1-X1 ~ factor(truth, exclude = NULL), data = lassoTrainResults00.1b[["pred"]],
     xlab = "Groups",
     ylab = "Predicted probability of cure")

dev.off()
```

Prediction at 2 months

Defining and showing 2-months data:

```
train.02.prot.1 <- visit2.prot.data
```

```
head(train.02.prot.1)
```

```
##      PID  SampleID  Donor      Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks Fever PrevdiagTB
## 1  260100 IQFT058411 TB Cures Training  50    1          1      2          2
## 2  360100 IQFT060811 TB Cures Training  70    2          1      1          2
## 3  950100 IQFT095511 TB Cures Training  70    1          2      2          2
## 4 1380100 IQFT025811 TB Cures Training  35    1          1      2          2
## 5 1790100 IQFT073111 TB Cures Training  70    2          2      2          1
## 6 2040100 IQFT061511 TB Cures Training  35    1          2      2          2
##  Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months BMI Severethinness IFNg IL10
## 1          2                2 17.99                2 205.62  7.27
## 2          2                2 12.20                1 337.95 35.28
## 3          1                2 18.10                2 305.68  0.97
## 4          2                2 19.13                2  54.84 69.21
## 5          2                2 20.56                2 379.65  1.62
## 6          2                1 17.57                2 2847.52  1.23
##  IL12p70  IL1b  IL4    TNFa  GMCSF IL15 IL17A  IL5   IL7   VEGF Eotaxin3
## 1  0.29  375.20 0.51  679.95  19.08 2.19  1.60 8.22  8.25 119.46  334.99
## 2  0.53  922.22 0.55 2247.00 139.99 2.88  2.02 0.84 12.97 109.64  361.55
## 3  0.31  177.99 0.06  346.56   6.87 2.77  1.53 1.14  8.09 323.23  471.45
## 4  1.08 1423.11 0.58  762.66  67.76 1.77  2.32 1.44 21.71  35.00 1047.50
## 5  0.12  159.04 0.38  155.10   8.94 1.24  4.17 2.95  6.34  23.04  436.58
## 6  0.22   93.07 0.55   65.21   3.15 1.98  1.73 7.88 10.88  33.72  605.12
##      IL8      IP10      MCP1      MDC      MIP1b
## 1 57984.20 5979.34 21569.58 1594.38 9591.49
## 2 694486.42 2967.99 67302.44 2147.60 28213.04
## 3 39506.72 6759.71 37999.96 2065.73 4651.42
## 4 846820.28 1508.75 55902.20 3121.09 63675.65
## 5 65777.52 6774.22 64026.42 2834.97 3808.02
## 6 29960.95 50187.82 26565.27 2248.18 12071.92
```

```
dim(train.02.prot.1)
```

```
## [1] 59 31
```

P

Fitting a LASSO logistic regression model only using basic participant characteristics (no marker data):

```
set.seed(201907014)
lassoTrainResults02.prot.0a <- lassoTrain(train.02.prot.1[, c(5:13)], train.02.prot.1[, 3],
                                          skipVar = 1:10)
lassoTrainResults02.prot.0a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 10 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##               1  1
## (Intercept)  0.45692962 NA
## Age          0.00000000 NA
## Gender       0.00000000 NA
## Cough.2weeks 0.00000000 NA
## Fever        0.00000000 NA
## PrevdiagTB   0.00000000 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.16084692 NA
## Alcoholpast6months 0.00000000 NA
## BMI          -0.04012869 NA
```

```
## Severethinness      -0.29694227 NA
lassoTrainResults02.prot.0a[["red.coef"]]

## 4 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##              1  1
## (Intercept)    0.45692962 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.16084692 NA
## BMI            -0.04012869 NA
## Severethinness  -0.29694227 NA

lassoTrainResults02.prot.0b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults02.prot.0a,
                                              train.02.prot.1[, c(5:13)], train.02.prot.1[, 3],
                                              "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")

rocObj.02.prot.0 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.prot.0b[["pred"]])
rocObj.02.prot.0

##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.prot.0b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 43 controls (truth TB Cures) < 16 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.7398

ci(rocObj.02.prot.0, of = "auc")

## 95% CI: 0.5856-0.8941 (DeLong)
aucMat.prot[1, 4:6] <- ci(rocObj.02.prot.0, of = "auc")
```

P+B

Fitting LASSO to basic participant characteristics and the selection of identified biomarkers (from step 1) using the criterion p-value less than 0.05:

```
set.seed(201907015)
lassoTrainResults02.prot.1a <- lassoTrain(train.02.prot.1[, -c(1:4)],
                                       train.02.prot.1[, 3], skipVar = 1:10)
lassoTrainResults02.prot.1a[["coef"]]

## 28 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##              1  1
## (Intercept) -1.040776624 NA
## Age         .          NA
## Gender      .          NA
## Cough.2weeks .         NA
## Fever       .          NA
## PrevdiagTB  .          NA
## Tobaccolast6months .     NA
## Alcoholpast6months .     NA
## BMI         .          NA
## Severethinness .        NA
## IFNg        .          .
## IL10        .          .
## IL12p70     .          .
## IL1b        .          .
```

```
## IL4 . .
## TNFa . .
## GMCSF . .
## IL15 . .
## IL17A . .
## IL5 . .
## IL7 0.003698923 100
## VEGF . .
## Eotaxin3 . .
## IL8 . .
## IP10 . .
## MCP1 . .
## MDC . .
## MIP1b . .
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.prot.1a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 2 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##          1 1
## (Intercept) -1.040776624 NA
## IL7          0.003698923 100
```

```
lassoTrainResults02.prot.1b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults02.prot.1a,
                                              train.02.prot.1[, -c(1:4)],
                                              train.02.prot.1[, 3], "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
rocObj.02.prot.1 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.prot.1b[["pred"]])
rocObj.02.prot.1
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.prot.1b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 43 controls (truth TB Cures) < 16 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.6788
```

```
ci(rocObj.02.prot.1, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.5144-0.8431 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.prot[2, 4:6] <- ci(rocObj.02.prot.1, of = "auc")
```

B

Fitting LASSO to selection of identified biomarkers without the basic participant characteristics:

```
set.seed(201907016)
lassoTrainResults02.prot.2a <- lassoTrain(train.02.prot.1[, -c(1:13)], train.02.prot.1[, 3])
lassoTrainResults02.prot.2a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 19 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##          1 1
## (Intercept) -1.2490891497 NA
## IFNg        . .
## IL10        . .
## IL12p70     . .
## IL1b        . .
## IL4         . .
```

```

## TNFa      .      .
## GMCSF     .      .
## IL15      .      .
## IL17A     .      .
## IL5       .      .
## IL7       0.0157257949 99
## VEGF      0.0001528811 1
## Eotaxin3  .      .
## IL8       .      .
## IP10      .      .
## MCP1      .      .
## MDC       .      .
## MIP1b     .      .
lassoTrainResults02.prot.2a[["red.coef"]]

## 3 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##           1 1
## (Intercept) -1.2490891497 NA
## IL7         0.0157257949 99
## VEGF        0.0001528811 1
lassoTrainResults02.prot.2b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults02.prot.2a,
                                              train.02.prot.1[, -c(1:13)], train.02.prot.1[, 3],
                                              "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")

rocObj.02.prot.2 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.prot.2b[["pred"]])
rocObj.02.prot.2

##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults02.prot.2b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 43 controls (truth TB Cures) < 16 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.6831
ci(rocObj.02.prot.2, of = "auc")

## 95% CI: 0.5114-0.8549 (DeLong)
aucMat.prot[3, 4:6] <- ci(rocObj.02.prot.2, of = "auc")

list.02.prot <- list(
  Basic = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.prot.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  BasicMarker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.prot.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Marker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.prot.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE])

idx.02.prot <- Reduce(union, lapply(list.02.prot, rownames))

combinedMat.02.prot <- do.call(cbind, lapply(list.02.prot, "[", idx.02.prot, ))
# code modified after:
# https://stackoverflow.com/questions/16808269/combine-data-frames-in-r-using-only-common-row-names
rownames(combinedMat.02.prot) <- idx.02.prot
combinedMat.02.prot

##           Basic BasicMarker      Marker
## (Intercept) 0.45692962 -1.040776624 -1.2490891497

```

```
## Tobaccolast6months -0.16084692      NA      NA
## BMI -0.04012869      NA      NA
## Severethinness -0.29694227      NA      NA
## IL7      NA 0.003698923 0.0157257949
## VEGF      NA      NA 0.0001528811
```

```
combinedMat.02.prot[-c(1:4), ] <- 1000*combinedMat.02.prot[-c(1:4), ]
```

```
combined.02.prot.mark <- combinedMat.02.prot[-c(1:4), ]
combined.02.prot.mark <- combined.02.prot.mark[order(row.names(combined.02.prot.mark)), ]
combinedMat.02.prot <- rbind(combinedMat.02.prot[1:4, ], combined.02.prot.mark)
combinedMat.02.prot
```

```
##           Basic BasicMarker      Marker
## (Intercept)  0.45692962 -1.040777 -1.2490891
## Tobaccolast6months -0.16084692      NA      NA
## BMI -0.04012869      NA      NA
## Severethinness -0.29694227      NA      NA
## IL7      NA  3.698923 15.7257949
## VEGF      NA      NA 0.1528811
```

```
print(xtable(combinedMat.02.prot, digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/combi")
```

Data for Figure 2, panel D

```
cbind(lassoTrainResults02.prot.1b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
      lassoTrainResults02.prot.0b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
      lassoTrainResults02.prot.2b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")])
```

##		truth	X1	truth	X1	truth
## 1	TB Cures	0.2669289		TB Cures	0.2349508	TB Cures
## 2	TB Cures	0.2703591		TB Cures	0.3427019	TB Cures
## 3	TB Cures	0.2668131		TB Cures	0.2642235	TB Cures
## 4	TB Cures	0.2767835		TB Cures	0.2268278	TB Cures
## 5	TB Cures	0.2655487		TB Cures	0.2169220	TB Cures
## 6	TB Cures	0.2688368		TB Cures	0.2379938	TB Cures
## 7	TB Cures	0.2747151		TB Cures	0.3204732	TB Cures
## 8	TB Cures	0.2686623		TB Cures	0.2801995	TB Cures
## 9	TB Cures	0.2696810		TB Cures	0.2273087	TB Cures
## 10	TB Cures	0.2772057		TB Cures	0.3097352	TB Cures
## 11	TB Cures	0.2732068		TB Cures	0.2414920	TB Cures
## 12	TB Cures	0.2709213		TB Cures	0.3225741	TB Cures
## 13	TB Cures	0.2673344		TB Cures	0.2276613	TB Cures
## 14	TB Cures	0.2687495		TB Cures	0.1334054	TB Cures
## 15	TB Cures	0.2710528		TB Cures	0.2451248	TB Cures
## 16	TB Cures	0.2714623		TB Cures	0.2469113	TB Cures
## 17	TB Cures	0.2701402		TB Cures	0.2776169	TB Cures
## 18	TB Cures	0.2655487		TB Cures	0.2598779	TB Cures
## 19	TB Cures	0.2680160		TB Cures	0.3106797	TB Cures
## 20	TB Cures	0.2683717		TB Cures	0.2505727	TB Cures
## 21	TB Cures	0.2683862		TB Cures	0.2489936	TB Cures
## 22	TB Cures	0.2710894		TB Cures	0.2472717	TB Cures
## 23	TB Cures	0.2657868		TB Cures	0.2198674	TB Cures
## 24	TB Cures	0.2635767		TB Cures	0.2625108	TB Cures
## 25	TB Cures	0.2715647		TB Cures	0.2290047	TB Cures

## 26	TB Cures	0.2750026	TB Cures	0.2728939	TB Cures
## 27	TB Cures	0.2681902	TB Cures	0.2193860	TB Cures
## 28	TB Cures	0.2670302	TB Cures	0.2708285	TB Cures
## 29	TB Cures	0.2710747	TB Cures	0.1900899	TB Cures
## 30	TB Cures	0.2689313	TB Cures	0.2240251	TB Cures
## 31	TB Cures	0.2676823	TB Cures	0.2783417	TB Cures
## 32	TB Cures	0.2663430	TB Cures	0.2156975	TB Cures
## 33	TB Cures	0.2720113	TB Cures	0.2794716	TB Cures
## 34	TB Cures	0.2681756	TB Cures	0.2095175	TB Cures
## 35	TB Cures	0.2754822	TB Cures	0.3183795	TB Cures
## 36	TB Cures	0.2771613	TB Cures	0.2366864	TB Cures
## 37	TB Cures	0.2707752	TB Cures	0.3545317	TB Cures
## 38	TB Cures	0.2725463	TB Cures	0.3471291	TB Cures
## 39	TB Cures	0.2670881	TB Cures	0.2607278	TB Cures
## 40	TB Cures	0.2749879	TB Cures	0.2642235	TB Cures
## 41	TB Cures	0.2781925	TB Cures	0.3216103	TB Cures
## 42	TB Cures	0.2687859	TB Cures	0.2447409	TB Cures
## 43	TB Cures	0.2659745	TB Cures	0.2541311	TB Cures
## 44	Treatment Failures	0.2643385	Treatment Failures	0.2173878	Treatment Failures
## 45	Treatment Failures	0.2693751	Treatment Failures	0.3210852	Treatment Failures
## 46	Treatment Failures	0.2683935	Treatment Failures	0.2732125	Treatment Failures
## 47	Treatment Failures	0.2789731	Treatment Failures	0.3410767	Treatment Failures
## 48	Treatment Failures	0.2761989	Treatment Failures	0.2271799	Treatment Failures
## 49	Treatment Failures	0.2680087	Treatment Failures	0.3546235	Treatment Failures
## 50	Treatment Failures	0.2764356	Treatment Failures	0.3495887	Treatment Failures
## 51	Treatment Failures	0.2779401	Treatment Failures	0.3552667	Treatment Failures
## 52	Treatment Failures	0.2693824	Treatment Failures	0.2498199	Treatment Failures
## 53	Treatment Failures	0.2931657	Treatment Failures	0.3456755	Treatment Failures
## 54	Treatment Failures	0.2722018	Treatment Failures	0.3624681	Treatment Failures
## 55	Treatment Failures	0.2686260	Treatment Failures	0.2491566	Treatment Failures
## 56	Treatment Failures	0.2735816	Treatment Failures	0.2800376	Treatment Failures
## 57	Treatment Failures	0.2831586	Treatment Failures	0.3840551	Treatment Failures
## 58	Treatment Failures	0.2736992	Treatment Failures	0.2715423	Treatment Failures
## 59	Treatment Failures	0.2703445	Treatment Failures	0.2705117	Treatment Failures
##	X1				
## 1	0.2495361				
## 2	0.2634015				
## 3	0.2549371				
## 4	0.2885716				
## 5	0.2412451				
## 6	0.2548639				
## 7	0.2862551				
## 8	0.2669973				
## 9	0.2576632				
## 10	0.2922849				
## 11	0.2742264				
## 12	0.2698928				
## 13	0.2494531				
## 14	0.2542505				
## 15	0.2640153				
## 16	0.2679718				
## 17	0.2606319				
## 18	0.2406269				
## 19	0.2509589				

```

## 20 0.2563552
## 21 0.2550844
## 22 0.2719501
## 23 0.2432225
## 24 0.2328857
## 25 0.2701414
## 26 0.2833549
## 27 0.2512866
## 28 0.2478277
## 29 0.2826328
## 30 0.2561511
## 31 0.2492667
## 32 0.2472126
## 33 0.2755090
## 34 0.2517958
## 35 0.2837829
## 36 0.3046873
## 37 0.2790909
## 38 0.2915725
## 39 0.2515018
## 40 0.2798601
## 41 0.3172209
## 42 0.2538441
## 43 0.2517079
## 44 0.2358921
## 45 0.2564013
## 46 0.2533020
## 47 0.3252776
## 48 0.3085117
## 49 0.2506306
## 50 0.2861183
## 51 0.3331121
## 52 0.2615923
## 53 0.3661514
## 54 0.2710101
## 55 0.2539232
## 56 0.2886999
## 57 0.3658775
## 58 0.2985850
## 59 0.2691866

```

```

print(xtable(cbind(lassoTrainResults02.prot.1b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
                  lassoTrainResults02.prot.0b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
                  lassoTrainResults02.prot.2b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")]),
      digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/fig2p

```

Making ROC curves

```

plot(rocObj.02.prot.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.02.prot.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.02.prot.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

```

```
legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.74", "Markers only: 0.68", "Basic + Markers: 0.68"),  
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)
```



```
plot(smooth(rocObj.02.prot.1), xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)  
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")  
  
plot(smooth(rocObj.02.prot.0), add = TRUE, lty = 2)  
  
plot(smooth(rocObj.02.prot.2), add = TRUE, lty = 3)
```


line: both basic characteristics and markers. Dashed line: basic characteristics only. Dotted line: markers only.

```
pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/roc02protv1.pdf")

plot(rocObj.02.prot.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.02.prot.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.02.prot.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.74", "Markers only: 0.68", "Basic + Markers: 0.68"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

dev.off()

## pdf
## 2

pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/prob02v1.pdf")

plot(1-X1 ~ factor(truth, exclude = NULL), data = lassoTrainResults02.1b[["pred"]],
      xlab = "Groups",
      ylab = "Predicted probability of cure")

dev.off()
```

Prediction at 6 months

```
train.06.prot.1 <- visit6.prot.data
```

```
head(train.06.prot.1)
```

```
##      PID   SampleID   Donor      Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks Fever PrevdiagTB
## 1  260100 IQFT105311 TB Cures Training  50      1         2      2         2
## 2  360100 IQFT107911 TB Cures Training  70      2         2      2         2
## 3  950100 IQFT155311 TB Cures Training  70      1         2      2         2
## 4 1380100 IQFT077711 TB Cures Training  35      1         2      2         2
## 5 1790100 IQFT123611 TB Cures Training  70      2         2      2         1
## 6 2040100 IQFT113011 TB Cures Training  35      1         2      2         2
##  Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months   BMI Severethinness   IFNg  IL10
## 1             2                         2 19.20                     2   77.94  7.36
## 2             2                         2 13.60                     1 109.04  3.57
## 3             1                         2 19.80                     2 281.92  1.27
## 4             2                         2 21.61                     2 205.03 26.13
## 5             2                         2 21.07                     2   31.01  1.01
## 6             2                         1 17.75                     2 1365.52  2.07
##  IL12p70   IL1b  IL4   TNFa  GMCSF  IL15  IL17A  IL5   IL7   VEGF  Eotaxin3
## 1    0.73  536.17  0.48 2244.69  44.59  1.94  2.37  2.25 11.56 104.23 1325.33
## 2    0.10  375.88  0.06  255.56  22.11  1.79  0.65  1.43  9.87 174.95  473.66
## 3    0.08  465.24  0.12  213.10  19.19  1.05  0.45  0.90  9.25 285.60  409.46
## 4    1.56 2238.69  1.11 3099.54 920.46  1.56  3.17  1.13 12.51 256.94 1526.14
## 5    0.30  330.47  0.09  329.35  17.16  1.06  0.28  0.74  5.53 131.84  263.08
## 6    0.18  394.89  0.36  309.96  19.80  1.51  0.80  3.21  8.28 111.13  468.43
##      IL8      IP10      MCP1      MDC      MIP1b
## 1 278542.81 1991.12 69937.09 1393.17 42146.75
## 2 118671.37 2939.91 75395.67 2371.79  7558.73
## 3  52636.66 6401.73 57322.28 1874.63  5794.50
## 4 610373.55 1109.70 32450.08 4394.02 50976.21
## 5 24715.83 1311.02 30907.81 1356.09 1938.41
## 6 38728.69 12281.16 40574.84 2255.65 14564.56
```

```
dim(train.06.prot.1)
```

```
## [1] 55 31
```

P

Fitting a LASSO logistic regression model only using basic participant characteristics (no marker data):

```
set.seed(201907017)
```

```
lassoTrainResults06.prot.0a <- lassoTrain(train.06.prot.1[, c(5:13)],
                                         train.06.prot.1[, 3], skipVar = 1:10)
```

```
lassoTrainResults06.prot.0a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 10 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##              1  1
## (Intercept)  2.82603063 NA
## Age          0.00000000 NA
## Gender       0.00000000 NA
## Cough.2weeks -0.79352957 NA
## Fever        -0.43651514 NA
```

```
## PrevdiagTB          0.00000000 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.36371655 NA
## Alcoholpast6months 0.00000000 NA
## BMI                 -0.05578472 NA
## Severethinness     -0.11501972 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults06.prot.0a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 6 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##              1  1
## (Intercept)  2.82603063 NA
## Cough.2weeks -0.79352957 NA
## Fever        -0.43651514 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.36371655 NA
## BMI          -0.05578472 NA
## Severethinness -0.11501972 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults06.prot.0b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults06.prot.0a,
                                              train.06.prot.1[, c(5:13)], train.06.prot.1[, 3],
                                              "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
```

```
rocObj.06.prot.0 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults06.prot.0b[["pred"]])
rocObj.06.prot.0
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults06.prot.0b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 41 controls (truth TB Cures) < 14 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.7909
```

```
ci(rocObj.06.prot.0, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.6438-0.9381 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.prot[1, 7:9] <- ci(rocObj.06.prot.0, of = "auc")
```

P+B

Fitting LASSO to basic participant characteristics and the selection of identified biomarkers (from step 1) using the criterion p-value less than 0.05:

```
set.seed(201907018)
```

```
lassoTrainResults06.prot.1a <- lassoTrain(train.06.prot.1[, -c(1:4)], train.06.prot.1[, 3])
lassoTrainResults06.prot.1a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 28 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##              1  1
## (Intercept) -0.3375512299 NA
## Age          .            .
## Gender       .            .
## Cough.2weeks -0.2815463687 26
## Fever        -0.6294327726 58
## PrevdiagTB   .            .
## Tobaccolast6months -0.0441581417 4
## Alcoholpast6months .            .
## BMI          .            .
```

```
## Severethinness      .      .
## IFNg                .      .
## IL10                .      .
## IL12p70             .      .
## IL1b                .      .
## IL4                 .      .
## TNFa                .      .
## GMCSF               .      .
## IL15                .      .
## IL17A               0.0272954724  2
## IL5                 .      .
## IL7                 0.1099771103  10
## VEGF                0.0006376002  0
## Eotaxin3           .      .
## IL8                 .      .
## IP10                .      .
## MCP1                .      .
## MDC                 -0.0003069042  0
## MIP1b               .      .
```

```
lassoTrainResults06.prot.1a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 8 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##                1  1
## (Intercept)    -0.3375512299 NA
## Cough.2weeks   -0.2815463687 26
## Fever          -0.6294327726 58
## Tobaccolast6months -0.0441581417 4
## IL17A          0.0272954724  2
## IL7            0.1099771103  10
## VEGF           0.0006376002  0
## MDC            -0.0003069042  0
```

```
lassoTrainResults06.prot.1b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults06.prot.1a,
                                              train.06.prot.1[, -c(1:4)],
                                              train.06.prot.1[, 3],
                                              "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
rocObj.06.prot.1 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults06.prot.1b[["pred"]])
rocObj.06.prot.1
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults06.prot.1b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 41 controls (truth TB Cures) < 14 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.9268
```

```
ci(rocObj.06.prot.1, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.8556-0.9981 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.prot[2, 7:9] <- ci(rocObj.06.prot.1, of = "auc")
```

B

Fitting LASSO to selection of identified biomarkers without the basic participant characteristics:

```

set.seed(201907019)
lassoTrainResults06.prot.2a <- lassoTrain(train.06.prot.1[, -c(1:13)], train.06.prot.1[, 3])
lassoTrainResults06.prot.2a[["coef"]]

## 19 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##               1 1
## (Intercept) -2.329514e+00 NA
## IFNg        2.767560e-06  0
## IL10         .           .
## IL12p70     .           .
## IL1b        .           .
## IL4         .           .
## TNFa        .           .
## GMCSF       .           .
## IL15        .           .
## IL17A       4.909987e-02 24
## IL5         .           .
## IL7         1.504978e-01 75
## VEGF        6.835432e-04  0
## Eotaxin3    .           .
## IL8         .           .
## IP10        .           .
## MCP1        8.111655e-07  0
## MDC         -5.219388e-04 0
## MIP1b       .           .

lassoTrainResults06.prot.2a[["red.coef"]]

## 7 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##               1 1
## (Intercept) -2.329514e+00 NA
## IFNg        2.767560e-06  0
## IL17A       4.909987e-02 24
## IL7         1.504978e-01 75
## VEGF        6.835432e-04  0
## MCP1        8.111655e-07  0
## MDC         -5.219388e-04 0

lassoTrainResults06.prot.2b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults06.prot.2a,
                                             train.06.prot.1[, -c(1:13)], train.06.prot.1[, 3],
                                             "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")

rocObj.06.prot.2 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults06.prot.2b[["pred"]])
rocObj.06.prot.2

##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults06.prot.2b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 41 controls (truth TB Cures) < 14 cases (truth Treatment Failures).
## Area under the curve: 0.9199

ci(rocObj.06.prot.2, of = "auc")

## 95% CI: 0.848-0.9917 (DeLong)

```

```

aucMat.prot[3, 7:9] <- ci(rocObj.06.prot.2, of = "auc")

list.06.prot <- list(
  Basic = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults06.prot.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  BasicMarker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults06.prot.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Marker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults06.prot.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE])

idx.06.prot <- Reduce(union, lapply(list.06.prot, rownames))

combinedMat.06.prot <- do.call(cbind, lapply(list.06.prot, "[", idx.06.prot, ))
# code modified after:
# https://stackoverflow.com/questions/16808269/combine-data-frames-in-r-using-only-common-row-names
rownames(combinedMat.06.prot) <- idx.06.prot
combinedMat.06.prot

```

##	Basic	BasicMarker	Marker
## (Intercept)	2.82603063	-0.3375512299	-2.329514e+00
## Cough.2weeks	-0.79352957	-0.2815463687	NA
## Fever	-0.43651514	-0.6294327726	NA
## Tobaccolast6months	-0.36371655	-0.0441581417	NA
## BMI	-0.05578472	NA	NA
## Severethinness	-0.11501972	NA	NA
## IL17A	NA	0.0272954724	4.909987e-02
## IL7	NA	0.1099771103	1.504978e-01
## VEGF	NA	0.0006376002	6.835432e-04
## MDC	NA	-0.0003069042	-5.219388e-04
## IFNg	NA	NA	2.767560e-06
## MCP1	NA	NA	8.111655e-07

```
combinedMat.06.prot[-c(1:6), ] <- 1000*combinedMat.06.prot[-c(1:6), ] # oops: hardcoded
```

```
combined.06.prot.mark <- combinedMat.06.prot[-c(1:6), ]
combined.06.prot.mark <- combined.06.prot.mark[order(row.names(combined.06.prot.mark)), ]
combinedMat.06.prot <- rbind(combinedMat.06.prot[1:6, ], combined.06.prot.mark)
combinedMat.06.prot
```

##	Basic	BasicMarker	Marker
## (Intercept)	2.82603063	-0.33755123	-2.329514e+00
## Cough.2weeks	-0.79352957	-0.28154637	NA
## Fever	-0.43651514	-0.62943277	NA
## Tobaccolast6months	-0.36371655	-0.04415814	NA
## BMI	-0.05578472	NA	NA
## Severethinness	-0.11501972	NA	NA
## IFNg	NA	NA	2.767560e-03
## IL17A	NA	27.29547239	4.909987e+01
## IL7	NA	109.97711035	1.504978e+02
## MCP1	NA	NA	8.111655e-04
## MDC	NA	-0.30690425	-5.219388e-01
## VEGF	NA	0.63760018	6.835432e-01

```
print(xtable(combinedMat.06.prot, digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/combi
```

```
plot(rocObj.06.prot.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")
```

```

plot(rocObj.06.prot.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.06.prot.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.79", "Markers only: 0.92", "Basic + Markers: 0.93"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

```



```

plot(smooth(rocObj.06.prot.1), xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(smooth(rocObj.06.prot.0), add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(smooth(rocObj.06.prot.2), add = TRUE, lty = 3)

```


Solid line: both basic characteristics and markers. Dashed line: basic characteristics only. Dotted line: markers only.

```
pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/roc06protv1.pdf")

plot(rocObj.06.prot.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.06.prot.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.06.prot.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.79", "Markers only: 0.92", "Basic + Markers: 0.93"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

dev.off()

## pdf
## 2

pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision//prob06protv1.pdf")

plot(1-X1 ~ factor(truth, exclude = NULL), data = lassoTrainResults06.1b[["pred"]],
     xlab = "Groups",
     ylab = "Predicted probability of cure")

dev.off()
```

AUC values

```
row.names(aucMat.prot) <- c("Basic", "Basic+Markers", "Markers")
colnames(aucMat.prot) <- c("CILO.0", "AUC.0", "CIHI.0", "CILO.2", "AUC.2", "CIHI.2", "CILO.6", "AUC.6",
aucMat.prot[, c(2, 1, 3)] # baseline

##                AUC.0   CILO.0   CIHI.0
## Basic          0.7773109 0.6766699 0.8779519
## Basic+Markers  0.8271309 0.7378179 0.9164439
## Markers        0.6914766 0.5715909 0.8113622

aucMat.prot[, c(5, 4, 6)] # 2 months

##                AUC.2   CILO.2   CIHI.2
## Basic          0.7398256 0.5855555 0.8940957
## Basic+Markers  0.6787791 0.5144149 0.8431433
## Markers        0.6831395 0.5113761 0.8549029

aucMat.prot[, c(8, 7, 9)] # 6 months

##                AUC.6   CILO.6   CIHI.6
## Basic          0.7909408 0.6437517 0.9381299
## Basic+Markers  0.9268293 0.8555929 0.9980656
## Markers        0.9198606 0.8480166 0.9917047

print(xtable(aucMat.prot[c(1, 3, 2), c(2, 1, 3, 5, 4, 6, 8, 7, 9)], digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/aucpr
```

Protein markers: Early responders - prediction at baseline

Defining the dataset:

```
train.02.early.prot.1 <- visit0.early.prot.data

head(train.02.early.prot.1)
```

```
##      PID  SampleID          Donor    Set Age Gender Cough.2weeks Fever
## 1   20400 IQFT141311 Early Responders Training  54    1      1      1
## 2   260100 IQFT030411 Early Responders Training  50    1      1      1
## 3   360100 IQFT031411 Early Responders Training  70    2      1      1
## 4   950100 IQFT074911 Early Responders Training  70    1      1      1
## 5  1050100 IQFT040111 Early Responders Training  29    1      1      2
## 6  1380100 IQFT008710 Early Responders Training  35    1      1      1
##     Prevdia TB Tobaccolast6months Alcoholpast6months  BMI Severethinness  IFNg
## 1           2              2                    2 16.99              2 122.63
## 2           2              2                    2 17.99              2 323.34
## 3           2              2                    2 13.14              1 735.69
## 4           2              2                    2 17.61              2 399.72
## 5           2              1                    1 15.98              1 1100.52
## 6           2              2                    2 16.48              2  51.88
##     IL10 IL12p70  IL1b  IL4    TNFa  GMCSF  IL15  IL17A  IL5   IL7   VEGF
## 1  1.08  0.17  691.72  0.04  424.57  18.12  5.09  1.40  0.16  13.54  479.68
## 2  2.43  0.58  712.30  0.28  582.69  7.87  2.41  2.26  5.35  10.61  98.05
## 3 34.40  1.43 1506.53  0.29 3668.05 124.18 3.55  0.55  0.25  21.05  260.90
## 4  2.28  0.20  733.73  0.19  400.10  14.67  1.53  0.57  0.93  9.77  281.79
```

```
## 5 11.22    0.31  678.66 0.24  588.96   4.54 2.37  0.30 0.51 14.96   2.14
## 6  4.35    0.30 1149.28 0.29  228.11   2.18 4.03  1.88 0.94 21.30 677.00
##   Eotaxin3      IL8      IP10      MCP1      MDC      MIP1b
## 1   400.63  32805.87  2734.65 16639.61  795.84  4253.43
## 2    93.67  64548.92 10868.44 25414.82 1338.10 11309.51
## 3   607.76 159617.58 16329.52 29705.85 1716.89 21394.59
## 4   254.21  32081.60  6703.45 19376.37 1751.86  5217.44
## 5    99.75 101965.91 25537.52 20446.35 1781.05 10217.95
## 6   286.55 640057.14  1164.40 11385.79 1888.89 12829.33
```

```
dim(train.02.early.prot.1)
```

```
## [1] 83 31
```

P

Fitting a LASSO logistic regression model only using basic participant characteristics (no marker data, only information about age, gender, cough (past 2 weeks), fever, previous diagnosed TB, tobacco (last 6 months), alcohol (past 6 months), BMI, and severe thinness):

```
set.seed(201911121)
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0a <- lassoTrain(train.02.early.prot.1[, c(5:13)],
                                                train.02.early.prot.1[, 3], skipVar = 1:10)
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 10 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##                1  1
## (Intercept)    3.05513153 NA
## Age            -0.01288819 NA
## Gender         -0.12903207 NA
## Cough.2weeks   0.00000000 NA
## Fever          0.00000000 NA
## PrevdiagTB     -0.35652344 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.29347432 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.40823465 NA
## BMI            0.00000000 NA
## Severethinness 0.00000000 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 6 x 2 Matrix of class "dgeMatrix"
##                1  1
## (Intercept)    3.05513153 NA
## Age            -0.01288819 NA
## Gender         -0.12903207 NA
## PrevdiagTB     -0.35652344 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.29347432 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.40823465 NA
```

```
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0a,
                                                    train.02.early.prot.1[, c(5:13)],
                                                    train.02.early.prot.1[, 3],
                                                    "Early Responders", "Non Responder")
```

```
rocObj.prot.00.early.0 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0b[["pred"]])
rocObj.prot.00.early.0
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 29 controls (truth Early Responders) < 54 cases (truth Non Responders).
## Area under the curve: 0.7404
ci(rocObj.prot.00.early.0, of = "auc")

## 95% CI: 0.6267-0.8541 (DeLong)
aucMat.prot.early <- matrix(NA, 3, 9)
aucMat.prot.early[1, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.prot.00.early.0, of = "auc")
```

B+P

Fitting LASSO to basic participant characteristics and the selection of identified biomarkers (from step 1) using the criterion p-value less than 0.05:

```
set.seed(201911122)
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1a <- lassoTrain(train.02.early.prot.1[, -c(1:4)],
                                              train.02.early.prot.1[, 3], skipVar = 1:10)
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1a[["coef"]]

## 28 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##              1  1
## (Intercept)  4.703344e+00 NA
## Age          -1.915653e-02 NA
## Gender       -2.999729e-01 NA
## Cough.2weeks .           NA
## Fever        .           NA
## PrevdiagTB   -1.184061e+00 NA
## Tobaccolast6months -1.727754e-01 NA
## Alcoholpast6months -6.796510e-01 NA
## BMI          .           NA
## Severethinness .           NA
## IFNg         .           .
## IL10         .           .
## IL12p70      .           .
## IL1b         2.252342e-04  0
## IL4         8.415608e-02  81
## TNFa        .           .
## GMCSF       .           .
## IL15        .           .
## IL17A       .           .
## IL5         .           .
## IL7         1.633649e-02  16
## VEGF        1.323137e-03  1
## Eotaxin3    1.353519e-03  1
## IL8         .           .
## IP10        2.607391e-06  0
## MCP1        .           .
## MDC         -5.512116e-04  1
## MIP1b       .           .
```

```
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 13 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"  
##              1  1  
## (Intercept)  4.703344e+00 NA  
## Age          -1.915653e-02 NA  
## Gender       -2.999729e-01 NA  
## PrevdiagTB   -1.184061e+00 NA  
## Tobaccolast6months -1.727754e-01 NA  
## Alcoholpast6months -6.796510e-01 NA  
## IL1b         2.252342e-04  0  
## IL4          8.415608e-02  81  
## IL7          1.633649e-02  16  
## VEGF         1.323137e-03  1  
## Eotaxin3     1.353519e-03  1  
## IP10         2.607391e-06  0  
## MDC          -5.512116e-04  1
```

```
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1a,  
                                                    train.02.early.prot.1[, -c(1:4)],  
                                                    train.02.early.prot.1[, 3],  
                                                    "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
```

```
rocObj.prot.00.early.1 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1b[["pred"]])  
rocObj.prot.00.early.1
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1b[["pred"]])  
##  
## Data: X1 in 29 controls (truth Early Responders) < 54 cases (truth Non Responders).  
## Area under the curve: 0.878
```

```
ci(rocObj.prot.00.early.1, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.8067-0.9494 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.prot.early[2, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.prot.00.early.1, of = "auc")
```

B

Fitting LASSO to selection of identified biomarkers without the basic participant characteristics:

```
set.seed(201911123)
```

```
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2a <- lassoTrain(train.02.early.prot.1[, -c(1:13)],  
                                              train.02.early.prot.1[, 3])  
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2a[["coef"]]
```

```
## 19 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"  
##              1  1  
## (Intercept)  1.768112e-02 NA  
## IFNg         .          .  
## IL10         .          .  
## IL12p70     .          .  
## IL1b        4.898819e-06  0
```

```
## IL4          5.385312e-01 94
## TNFa         .           .
## GMCSF        .           .
## IL15         .           .
## IL17A        .           .
## IL5          .           .
## IL7          3.167723e-02 6
## VEGF         8.860677e-04 0
## Eotaxin3     8.981144e-04 0
## IL8          .           .
## IP10         2.831600e-06 0
## MCP1         .           .
## MDC          -5.229358e-04 0
## MIP1b        .           .
```

```
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2a[["red.coef"]]
```

```
## 8 x 2 sparse Matrix of class "dgCMatrix"
##              1 1
## (Intercept) 1.768112e-02 NA
## IL1b        4.898819e-06 0
## IL4         5.385312e-01 94
## IL7         3.167723e-02 6
## VEGF        8.860677e-04 0
## Eotaxin3    8.981144e-04 0
## IP10        2.831600e-06 0
## MDC         -5.229358e-04 0
```

```
lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2b <- lassoValidation(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2a,
  train.02.early.prot.1[, -c(1:13)],
  train.02.early.prot.1[, 3],
  "TB Cures", "Treatment Failures")
```

```
rocObj.prot.00.early.2 <- roc(truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2b[["pred"]])
rocObj.prot.00.early.2
```

```
##
## Call:
## roc.formula(formula = truth ~ X1, data = lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2b[["pred"]])
##
## Data: X1 in 29 controls (truth Early Responders) < 54 cases (truth Non Responders).
## Area under the curve: 0.7829
```

```
ci(rocObj.prot.00.early.2, of = "auc")
```

```
## 95% CI: 0.6826-0.8832 (DeLong)
```

```
aucMat.prot.early[3, 1:3] <- ci(rocObj.prot.00.early.2, of = "auc")
```

```
list.prot.00.early <- list(
  Basic = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE]
  BasicMarker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE]
  Marker = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE]
```

```
idx.prot.00.early <- Reduce(union, lapply(list.prot.00.early, rownames))
```

```
combinedMat.prot.00.early <- do.call(cbind, lapply(list.prot.00.early, "[", idx.prot.00.early, ))
```

```

# code modified after:
# https://stackoverflow.com/questions/16808269/combine-data-frames-in-r-using-only-common-row-names
rownames(combinedMat.prot.00.early) <- idx.prot.00.early
combinedMat.prot.00.early

##              Basic  BasicMarker  Marker
## (Intercept)  3.05513153  4.703344e+00  1.768112e-02
## Age          -0.01288819 -1.915653e-02  NA
## Gender       -0.12903207 -2.999729e-01  NA
## PrevdiagTB   -0.35652344 -1.184061e+00  NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.29347432 -1.727754e-01  NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.40823465 -6.796510e-01  NA
## IL1b         NA  2.252342e-04  4.898819e-06
## IL4         NA  8.415608e-02  5.385312e-01
## IL7         NA  1.633649e-02  3.167723e-02
## VEGF        NA  1.323137e-03  8.860677e-04
## Eotaxin3    NA  1.353519e-03  8.981144e-04
## IP10        NA  2.607391e-06  2.831600e-06
## MDC         NA  -5.512116e-04 -5.229358e-04

combinedMat.prot.00.early[-c(1:6), ] <- 1000*combinedMat.prot.00.early[-c(1:6), ] # OOPS: 1.6 is hardc

combined.prot.00.early.mark <- combinedMat.prot.00.early[-c(1:6), ]
combined.prot.00.early.mark <- combined.prot.00.early.mark[order(row.names(combined.prot.00.early.mark))]
combinedMat.prot.00.early <- rbind(combinedMat.prot.00.early[1:6, ], combined.prot.00.early.mark)
combinedMat.prot.00.early

```

```

##              Basic  BasicMarker  Marker
## (Intercept)  3.05513153  4.703343653  0.017681119
## Age          -0.01288819 -0.019156528  NA
## Gender       -0.12903207 -0.299972943  NA
## PrevdiagTB   -0.35652344 -1.184060946  NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.29347432 -0.172775359  NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.40823465 -0.679651048  NA
## Eotaxin3    NA  1.353518932  0.898114442
## IL1b         NA  0.225234234  0.004898819
## IL4         NA  84.156079365  538.531193862
## IL7         NA  16.336488938  31.677228987
## IP10        NA  0.002607391  0.002831600
## MDC         NA  -0.551211591 -0.522935808
## VEGF        NA  1.323137370  0.886067710

print(xtable(combinedMat.prot.00.early, digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/combini

```

Data for Figure 4, panel B

```

cbind(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
      lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],
      lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")])

##          truth      X1          truth      X1          truth
## 1 Early Responders 0.60389039 Early Responders 0.5283875 Early Responders
## 2 Early Responders 0.32677177 Early Responders 0.5412125 Early Responders
## 3 Early Responders 0.41607807 Early Responders 0.4448328 Early Responders
## 4 Early Responders 0.28885639 Early Responders 0.4768818 Early Responders

```


## 59	Non Responders	0.86077261	Non Responders	0.7427396	Non Responders
## 60	Non Responders	0.75093057	Non Responders	0.7293782	Non Responders
## 61	Non Responders	0.90654506	Non Responders	0.7013820	Non Responders
## 62	Non Responders	0.90008476	Non Responders	0.7242603	Non Responders
## 63	Non Responders	0.80145451	Non Responders	0.7424736	Non Responders
## 64	Non Responders	0.79216087	Non Responders	0.6574322	Non Responders
## 65	Non Responders	0.84990728	Non Responders	0.7793912	Non Responders
## 66	Non Responders	0.87662404	Non Responders	0.6856092	Non Responders
## 67	Non Responders	0.85394161	Non Responders	0.7327665	Non Responders
## 68	Non Responders	0.69362087	Non Responders	0.6651524	Non Responders
## 69	Non Responders	0.89412241	Non Responders	0.7642730	Non Responders
## 70	Non Responders	0.79303552	Non Responders	0.7945118	Non Responders
## 71	Non Responders	0.88743823	Non Responders	0.7173542	Non Responders
## 72	Non Responders	0.87800425	Non Responders	0.6886450	Non Responders
## 73	Non Responders	0.95875878	Non Responders	0.7619431	Non Responders
## 74	Non Responders	0.61132706	Non Responders	0.7251274	Non Responders
## 75	Non Responders	0.48671490	Non Responders	0.5412125	Non Responders
## 76	Non Responders	0.74305841	Non Responders	0.6278818	Non Responders
## 77	Non Responders	0.67732909	Non Responders	0.6651524	Non Responders
## 78	Non Responders	0.79714490	Non Responders	0.6651877	Non Responders
## 79	Non Responders	0.70094134	Non Responders	0.7476340	Non Responders
## 80	Non Responders	0.47578812	Non Responders	0.5910921	Non Responders
## 81	Non Responders	0.58688277	Non Responders	0.6765698	Non Responders
## 82	Non Responders	0.81619384	Non Responders	0.6687067	Non Responders
## 83	Non Responders	0.83302366	Non Responders	0.6248656	Non Responders
##	X1				
## 1		0.7001330			
## 2		0.5025236			
## 3		0.6842710			
## 4		0.5034872			
## 5		0.4642026			
## 6		0.6741382			
## 7		0.2733293			
## 8		0.6445179			
## 9		0.5155197			
## 10		0.6261725			
## 11		0.7355612			
## 12		0.5730508			
## 13		0.6115170			
## 14		0.7340560			
## 15		0.6319135			
## 16		0.5798942			
## 17		0.7382346			
## 18		0.5609723			
## 19		0.6106814			
## 20		0.4256704			
## 21		0.5559216			
## 22		0.4328194			
## 23		0.5888367			
## 24		0.2912610			
## 25		0.5505159			
## 26		0.1437022			
## 27		0.3569282			
## 28		0.4856806			

29 0.7197271
30 0.7464742
31 0.5596917
32 0.7906771
33 0.9296861
34 0.5965646
35 0.5666372
36 0.5726968
37 0.6988077
38 0.8848780
39 0.6772493
40 0.6641079
41 0.5879729
42 0.8441311
43 0.8963106
44 0.5409722
45 0.9570300
46 0.6457484
47 0.6329013
48 0.7129414
49 0.6814623
50 0.7191803
51 0.5574116
52 0.6731261
53 0.5870830
54 0.6296978
55 0.8164902
56 0.6967094
57 0.6190421
58 0.7510961
59 0.7482465
60 0.5378208
61 0.8746271
62 0.8105028
63 0.5030341
64 0.7609847
65 0.6878474
66 0.8543307
67 0.7588085
68 0.5787396
69 0.8189937
70 0.5541482
71 0.8049626
72 0.7944860
73 0.9558420
74 0.5656368
75 0.6687458
76 0.7871216
77 0.5828579
78 0.7701304
79 0.6158486
80 0.6141598
81 0.5663152
82 0.7702807

```
## 83 0.8635117
```

```
print(xtable(cbind(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],  
                  lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")],  
                  lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2b[["pred"]][, c("truth", "X1")]),  
      digits = 4), type = "html",  
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/fig4p
```

Making ROC curves

```
plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)  
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")  
  
plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)  
  
plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)  
  
legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.74", "Markers only: 0.78", "Basic + Markers: 0.88"),  
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)
```



```
plot(smooth(rocObj.prot.00.early.1), xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)  
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")  
  
plot(smooth(rocObj.prot.00.early.0), add = TRUE, lty = 2)  
  
plot(smooth(rocObj.prot.00.early.2), add = TRUE, lty = 3)
```


line: both basic characteristics and markers. Dashed line: basic characteristics only. Dotted line: markers only.

```
pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/rocprot02early
```

```
plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")
```

```
plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)
```

```
plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)
```

```
legend("bottomright", legend = c("Basic only: 0.74", "Markers only: 0.78", "Basic + Markers: 0.88"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)
```

```
dev.off()
```

```
list.02YY <- list(
```

```
  Patient00 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.prot.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Biomarker00 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.prot.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient.Biomarker00 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults00.prot.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient02 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.prot.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Biomarker02 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.prot.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient.Biomarker02 = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults02.prot.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient00.E = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.0a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Biomarker00.E = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.2a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE],
  Patient.Biomarker00.E = as.data.frame(as.matrix(lassoTrainResults.prot.00.early.1a[["red.coef"]]))[, 1, drop = FALSE]
```

```
idx.02Y <- Reduce(union, lapply(list(pat.dat, list.02YY[["Patient00"]], list.02YY[["Patient02"]],
  list.02YY[["Patient00.E"]], list.02YY[["Patient.Biomarker00"]], list.02YY[["Patient02.E"]], list.02YY[["Patient.Biomarker02"]], list.02YY[["Patient00.E"]], list.02YY[["Patient.Biomarker00"]], list.02YY[["Patient02.E"]], list.02YY[["Patient.Biomarker02"]]),
```

```

list.02YY[["Biomarker00"]], list.02YY[["Biomarker02"]],
list.02YY[["Biomarker00.E"]]), rownames))
idx.02Y

## [1] "(Intercept)"      "Age"                "Alcoholpast6months"
## [4] "BMI"              "Gender"             "Cough.2weeks"
## [7] "Fever"           "PrevdiagTB"        "Severethinness"
## [10] "Tobaccolast6months" "GMCSF"             "IL7"
## [13] "Eotaxin3"        "MDC"               "IL1b"
## [16] "IL4"             "VEGF"              "IP10"

idx.02YY <- c(idx.02Y[1:10], sort(idx.02Y[-c(1:10)]))

idx.02YY

## [1] "(Intercept)"      "Age"                "Alcoholpast6months"
## [4] "BMI"              "Gender"             "Cough.2weeks"
## [7] "Fever"           "PrevdiagTB"        "Severethinness"
## [10] "Tobaccolast6months" "Eotaxin3"          "GMCSF"
## [13] "IL1b"            "IL4"               "IL7"
## [16] "IP10"            "MDC"               "VEGF"

combinedMat.02YY <- do.call(cbind, lapply(list.02YY, "[", idx.02YY, ))
# code modified after:
# https://stackoverflow.com/questions/16808269/combine-data-frames-in-r-using-only-common-row-names
rownames(combinedMat.02YY) <- idx.02YY
combinedMat.02YY

```

```

##           Patient00  Biomarker00 Patient.Biomarker00  Patient02
## (Intercept)  4.559328686 -0.9129200563      2.9571466292  0.45692962
## Age          -0.007040029      NA                NA                NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.263409467      NA                -0.4249319393      NA
## BMI          NA                NA                NA                -0.04012869
## Gender       -0.969723323      NA                -0.5714076217      NA
## Cough.2weeks      NA                NA                NA                NA
## Fever         NA                NA                NA                NA
## PrevdiagTB      -0.391895879      NA                -0.4778040420      NA
## Severethinness -0.933178239      NA                -0.7195372003 -0.29694227
## Tobaccolast6months -0.647060236      NA                -0.3923779153 -0.16084692
## Eotaxin3        NA                NA                0.0002167213      NA
## GMCSF          NA                0.0020843034      0.0038132121      NA
## IL1b          NA                NA                NA                NA
## IL4           NA                NA                NA                NA
## IL7           NA                0.0447180963      0.0406383184      NA
## IP10          NA                NA                NA                NA
## MDC           NA                -0.0001552075     -0.0002074590      NA
## VEGF          NA                NA                NA                NA
##           Biomarker02 Patient.Biomarker02 Patient00.E Biomarker00.E
## (Intercept) -1.2490891497      -1.040776624  3.05513153  1.768112e-02
## Age          NA                NA                NA                -0.01288819
## Alcoholpast6months NA                NA                NA                -0.40823465
## BMI          NA                NA                NA                NA
## Gender       NA                NA                NA                -0.12903207
## Cough.2weeks NA                NA                NA                NA
## Fever         NA                NA                NA                NA
## PrevdiagTB   NA                NA                NA                -0.35652344

```

```

## Severethinness          NA          NA          NA          NA
## Tobaccolast6months     NA          NA -0.29347432          NA
## Eotaxin3               NA          NA          NA 8.981144e-04
## GMCSF                  NA          NA          NA          NA
## IL1b                   NA          NA          NA 4.898819e-06
## IL4                     NA          NA          NA 5.385312e-01
## IL7                     0.0157257949    0.003698923    NA 3.167723e-02
## IP10                    NA          NA          NA 2.831600e-06
## MDC                     NA          NA          NA -5.229358e-04
## VEGF                    0.0001528811    NA          NA 8.860677e-04
## Patient.Biomarker00.E
## (Intercept)             4.703344e+00
## Age                     -1.915653e-02
## Alcoholpast6months     -6.796510e-01
## BMI                     NA
## Gender                  -2.999729e-01
## Cough.2weeks           NA
## Fever                   NA
## PrevdiagTB             -1.184061e+00
## Severethinness         NA
## Tobaccolast6months     -1.727754e-01
## Eotaxin3                1.353519e-03
## GMCSF                   NA
## IL1b                    2.252342e-04
## IL4                     8.415608e-02
## IL7                     1.633649e-02
## IP10                    2.607391e-06
## MDC                     -5.512116e-04
## VEGF                    1.323137e-03

```

```
combinedMat.02YY[-c(1:10), ] <- 1000*combinedMat.02YY[-c(1:10), ]
```

```
combinedMat.02YY
```

```

## Patient00 Biomarker00 Patient.Biomarker00 Patient02
## (Intercept) 4.559328686 -0.9129201 2.9571466 0.45692962
## Age -0.007040029 NA NA NA
## Alcoholpast6months -0.263409467 NA -0.4249319 NA
## BMI NA NA NA -0.04012869
## Gender -0.969723323 NA -0.5714076 NA
## Cough.2weeks NA NA NA NA
## Fever NA NA NA NA
## PrevdiagTB -0.391895879 NA -0.4778040 NA
## Severethinness -0.933178239 NA -0.7195372 -0.29694227
## Tobaccolast6months -0.647060236 NA -0.3923779 -0.16084692
## Eotaxin3 NA NA 0.2167213 NA
## GMCSF NA 2.0843034 3.8132121 NA
## IL1b NA NA NA NA
## IL4 NA NA NA NA
## IL7 NA 44.7180963 40.6383184 NA
## IP10 NA NA NA NA
## MDC NA -0.1552075 -0.2074590 NA
## VEGF NA NA NA NA
## Biomarker02 Patient.Biomarker02 Patient00.E Biomarker00.E
## (Intercept) -1.2490891 -1.040777 3.05513153 0.017681119

```

```

## Age NA NA -0.01288819 NA
## Alcoholpast6months NA NA -0.40823465 NA
## BMI NA NA NA NA
## Gender NA NA -0.12903207 NA
## Cough.2weeks NA NA NA NA
## Fever NA NA NA NA
## PrevdiagTB NA NA -0.35652344 NA
## Severethinness NA NA NA NA
## Tobaccolast6months NA NA -0.29347432 NA
## Eotaxin3 NA NA NA 0.898114442
## GMCSF NA NA NA NA
## IL1b NA NA NA 0.004898819
## IL4 NA NA NA 538.531193862
## IL7 15.7257949 3.698923 NA 31.677228987
## IP10 NA NA NA 0.002831600
## MDC NA NA NA -0.522935808
## VEGF 0.1528811 NA NA 0.886067710
## Patient.Biomarker00.E
## (Intercept) 4.703343653
## Age -0.019156528
## Alcoholpast6months -0.679651048
## BMI NA
## Gender -0.299972943
## Cough.2weeks NA
## Fever NA
## PrevdiagTB -1.184060946
## Severethinness NA
## Tobaccolast6months -0.172775359
## Eotaxin3 1.353518932
## GMCSF NA
## IL1b 0.225234234
## IL4 84.156079365
## IL7 16.336488938
## IP10 0.002607391
## MDC -0.551211591
## VEGF 1.323137370

```

```

print(xtable(combinedMat.02YY, digits = 4), type = "html",
      file = "/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/combinedMat.02YY.html")

```

Creating Figure 2

```

pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/roc02v1YY.pdf")

```

```

par(mfrow = c(2, 2))

```

```

plot(rocObj.00.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

```

```

plot(rocObj.00.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

```

```

plot(rocObj.00.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

```

```

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Patient only: 0.78", "Markers only: 0.78", "Patient + Markers: 0.89"),
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), lwd = 2, bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

```

```

text(1,1, "A", cex = 1.3)

plot(rocObj.00.prot.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.00.prot.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.00.prot.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Patient only: 0.77", "Markers only: 0.69", "Patient + Markers: 0.83")
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), lwd = 2, bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

text(1,1, "C", cex = 1.3)

plot(rocObj.02.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.02.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.02.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Patient only: 0.83", "Markers only: 0.84", "Patient + Markers: 0.97")
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), lwd = 2, bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

text(1,1, "B", cex = 1.3)

plot(rocObj.02.prot.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.02.prot.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.02.prot.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Patient only: 0.74", "Markers only: 0.68", "Patient + Markers: 0.68")
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), lwd = 2, bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

text(1,1, "D", cex = 1.3)

dev.off()

## pdf
## 2

Creating Figure 4

pdf("/home/christian/stat/collaboration/NEXS/DhanaSivakumaran/2018-TB treatment/revision/roc02v1ZZ.pdf")

par(mfrow = c(2, 2))

plot(rocObj.00.early.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

```

```

plot(rocObj.00.early.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.00.early.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Patient only: 0.77", "Markers only: 0.67", "Patient + Markers: 0.97")
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), lwd = 2, bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

text(1,1, "A", cex = 1.3)

plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.1, xlim = c(1, 0), identity = FALSE)
segments(1, 0, 0, 1, col = "lightgray")

plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.0, add = TRUE, lty = 2)

plot(rocObj.prot.00.early.2, add = TRUE, lty = 3)

legend("bottomright", legend = c("Patient only: 0.74", "Markers only: 0.78", "Patient + Markers: 0.88")
      lty = c(2, 3, 1), lwd = 2, bty = "n", title = "Estimated AUC values", title.adj = 0)

text(1,1, "B", cex = 1.3)

dev.off()

## pdf
## 2

```